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1 st	15/12/2023	Kalliopi Kounani/ Anastasia Kannavou	Added the section of the interviews.
2 nd	8/01/2023	Kalliopi Kounani	Finalised the interviews section added the ones missing in the first revision.
3 rd	27/11/2024	Marjan Vooijs (WR)	Disclaimer has been added to the front page.

Executive summary of the deliverable

There is a general consensus among both the public and the scientific community that there is a need to move away from food systems focused on chemical pesticides (Aktar et al, 2009; Bakker et al, 2021; Chagnon et al, 2015; Koehler & Triebkorn, 2013; Mustafa et al, 2021; Sharma et al, 2019, 2020; Tang et al, 2021, 2022; Wuepper et al, 2023). At the Fifteenth Meeting of the Parties to the United Nations Convention on Biological Diversity (COP15), the EU and all EU Member States adopted the historic Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework¹ and set themselves the globally binding target of "reducing the overall risk from pesticides and highly hazardous chemicals by at least half by 2030, including through integrated pest management (IPM), based on science, taking into account food security and livelihoods".

Future strategies and policies need to be developed to reduce the use and risks of pesticides, supporting agricultural production and food security and encouraging the development and adoption of sustainable practices.

The SUPPORT analyses why adoption of IPM and low pesticide input practices is lagging behind objectives and expectations. The project creates solutions by building on an RRI approach, in particular referring to the analysis of the barriers and opportunities in the external environment, which need to be matched with the understanding of the reasons why farmers and growers decide to apply IPM, low-risk pesticide use practices or rely on chemical pesticide use. This matching process creates a basis for the development of strategies to enable and support individual farmers to apply IPM and to make their crop protection management more sustainable. It will help them to make use of the existing opportunities. Furthermore, it creates the basis for the development of strategies and policies at the level of systems, landscape and rural areas to remove barriers, to create new opportunities and to enable farmer systems to adopt IPM and low-risk pesticide use practices at a larger scale. Finally, it provides the basis for adjustment of crop protection policies at member state and EU level.

WP3 SUPPORT 'Policy and strategy analysis and design' aims to develop the strategies and policy recommendations in co-creation with actors in a transdisciplinary multi-actor approach. AUA has developed the D3.1 "Policy Analysis" report, which reviews existing IPM strategic and policy framework to identify policy gaps and needs at EU and across selected Member States level.

¹ [Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework](#)

Contents

Executive summary of the deliverable	4
Table of Abbreviations and Acronyms	6
1. Introduction	7
2. Methodology	8
3. Desktop Research: Integrated Pest Management- related policies	10
3.1 Integrated pest management (IPM)	10
3.2 IPM-related policies at EU level	15
3.3. IPM-related policies at national level	22
3.3.1 National Action Plans	22
3.3.2. CAP Strategic Plans (CSPs)	33
4. Research and Innovation.....	51
5. Interview-Based Policy Assessment	54
5.1 EU Level Interviews Analysis.....	54
5.1 MS Level Interviews Analysis	54
1) Germany:.....	54
2) Italy:	55
3) Belgium:	56
4) Poland:	56
5) Romania:	57
6) Netherlands:.....	58
7) Denmark:.....	58
8) Spain.....	59
9) Greece.....	60
6. Synthesis of information	61
6.1 Desktop Research.....	61
6.2 Interviews Analysis.....	67
6. Conclusion - Policy Gaps and Needs.....	69
7. References	72
ANNEX I	74
Interview guidelines for Member State Policy Makers	74
INTRODUCTION	74
IDENTIFICATION QUESTIONS.....	75
THEME 1 - Policy Framework Assessment.....	75
THEME 2 - Specific needs and challenges	78
THEME 3 - Stakeholder engagement.....	80
THEME 4 - Role of research and innovation.....	81
Interview guidelines for EU Policy Makers	82
INTRODUCTION	82
IDENTIFICATION QUESTIONS.....	83

Table of Abbreviations and Acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
GA	The General Assembly
CA	Consortium Agreement
SC	Scientific Coordinator
PM	Project Manager
PMO	Project Management Officer
PMT	The Project Management Team
EB	Executive Board (Core Team)
WP	The Work Package
WPL	The Work Package Leader
TL	Task leader
NCC	National Crop Cluster
CoP	Community of Practices
NoP	Network of Practices
PAB	Project Advisory Board
SCT	Scientific Coordination Team
DoA	Description of the action

1. Introduction

WP3 SUPPORT 'Policy and strategy analysis and design' aims to develop the strategies and policy recommendations in co-creation with actors in a transdisciplinary multi-actor approach. AUA has developed the D3.1 "Policy Analysis" report, which reviews existing IPM-related strategic and policy framework to identify policy gaps and needs at EU level and across selected Member States. We will explore the commonalities and disparities among the IPM-related policies of nine EU Member States through extensive desktop research and interviews with Policy Makers at EU level and Member state level, specifically examining their National Action Plans (NAPs) and their CAP Strategic Plans (CSPs). These member states are Belgium, Denmark, Germany, Greece, Italy, Netherlands, Poland, Romania, and Spain. Our goal is to gain a comprehensive understanding of how the EU and in particular these countries regulate, monitor, assess and incentivize IPM practices.

2. Methodology

The desktop research initiates by establishing the identification of a key research question: “What are the strategies, initiatives, policies, and legislative documents that impact Integrated Pest Management (IPM) at regional, national, and EU levels, and what are the policy gaps and requirements specific to each region, cropping system, and agri-food supply chain?”. To address this question, a comprehensive policy literature review has been conducted. This review aims to evaluate the impact of various strategies, initiatives, policies, and legislative documents on the implementation of IPM. Additionally, it seeks to pinpoint policy gaps and determine specific needs concerning different regions, cropping systems, and agri-food supply chains.

The desk research involved the consolidation of information sources publicly available (EU and national government publications, academic articles, reports, books, websites and databases) that were identified as being reliable and containing relevant information on the sustainable use of pesticides and the implementation of the IPM to underpin the analysis. Following the consolidation of sources, the literature was then coded and categorised based on a number of parameters (i.e. tags) to help organise and operationalise the information for its use in the analysis. The field research comprised of interviews targeted to EU and MSs policy makers, policy officers and decision makers. The collected data fed into answering the research questions. Proper citation of all information and data used in the research was done to ensure accuracy and consistency. The findings were summarized and presented in a clear and organized manner. To enhance the quality of the research, the findings were shared with members of the advisory board to gain valuable insights and validation.

For the Interviewers, the methodology implemented for this study was designed to scrutinize policy frameworks and elicit recommendations that could potentially enhance region-specific policies, cropping systems, and the agri-food supply chain. In total, 34 interviews (Annex I) were conducted: two with European Union level policy makers and thirty-two with Member State level policy makers, with an equitable distribution of four interviews per Community of Practice (CoP).

These structured interviews served as a tool for identifying existing policy gaps and garnering a multifaceted understanding of the integrated pest management (IPM) landscape. The discussions facilitated with policy makers were instrumental in unravelling the intricacies of the current policies and their operational challenges. By employing a standardized questionnaire as the foundation for these interviews, we ensured that each conversation was focused and yielded data that could be reliably compared and contrasted.

The interview process was structured to foster an environment where policy makers could freely express the unique needs and challenges encountered within their respective policy environments. This approach not only highlighted regional differences but also allowed for the aggregation of common themes that might benefit from a more unified policy strategy. The insights gleaned from these dialogues will be pivotal in informing the subsequent multi-actor co-creation workshops (T3.2) and in formulating robust policy recommendations (T3.3).

In aligning with the objectives of this task, the interview findings will contribute to a comprehensive analysis of the current policy landscape, underpin the development of targeted policy interventions, and set the groundwork for enhanced collaborative efforts among stakeholders in the IPM domain.

The analysis of the Interview Questions followed the below mentioned methodology:

1. Initial Reading

An initial reading of the documents was conducted to grasp the general content, context, and structure of the interviews.

2. Identifying Themes and Categories

Thematic Analysis: Patterns (themes) within the data were identified, analysed, and reported. During the reading of the interviews, recurring topics, concepts, opinions, and terms were noted.

Categorization: These themes were categorized accordingly. For instance, discussions about the Sustainable Use Directive (SUD), Integrated Pest Management (IPM), or the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) were grouped under relevant categories such as policy implementation, agricultural practices, etc.

3. Comparison and Contrast

Cross-document Analysis: Themes identified within each interview were compared across all documents. This step was essential for understanding similarities and differences in content, focus, or opinion.

Delineating Differences and Similarities: Statements, opinions, or facts that aligned or differed between the interviews were noted as common themes or points of divergence.

4. Contextual Understanding

Understanding the Broader Context: A broad understanding of topics including EU policies, agricultural practices, and environmental regulations was applied to contextualize the interview content.

Integrating External Knowledge: Where relevant, pre-existing knowledge was integrated into the analysis to provide depth and context, especially when understanding such complex themes.

5. Synthesis and Summarization

Drawing Conclusions: Based on the thematic analysis, comparison, and contextual understanding, main findings from the interviews were synthesized.

Summarization: These findings were then distilled into a concise summary, emphasizing key points, similarities, and differences, ensuring accurate representation of the interviews' essence.

3. Desktop Research: Integrated Pest Management- related policies

This chapter initially introduces the concept of Integrated Pest Management (IPM) and subsequently outlines the policy and legislative framework related to IPM at both the EU and national levels for the participating Member States in the project—Belgium, Denmark, France, Germany, Greece, Italy, Netherlands, Poland, Romania, and Spain, as of October 2023.

3.1 Integrated pest management (IPM)

A 'pesticide' is something that prevents, destroys, or controls a harmful organism ('pest') or disease, or protects plants or plant products during production, storage and transport. The term includes, amongst others: herbicides, fungicides, insecticides, acaricides, nematocides, molluscicides, growth regulators, repellents, rodenticides and biocides ([EC, Food Safety](#)).

Plant protection products (PPPs) are pesticides used to fight plant pests and diseases, and to control weeds. PPP uses occur mainly in agriculture, but also in forestry and green urban areas. PPPs contain at least one active substance; the active substances can be chemicals or microorganisms. PPPs might be harmful to human health and the environment, and are thus a source of concern for citizens. Therefore, the marketing of pesticides that are PPPs, their use in a sustainable way and their maximum residue levels in food and feed, as well as relevant statistics, are subject to legal regulation at EU level (EPRS, 2022).

The term 'pesticide' is often used interchangeably with 'plant protection product', even in the EU legislation. However, pesticide is a broader term that also covers non plant/crop uses, for example biocides. In this report the term 'pesticide' is used synonymously with the term 'plant protection product' (PPP). The term 'pesticide', in the context of this report, refers to plant protection products (PPPs) as defined by Article 3 (10)(a) of Directive 2009/128/EC.

Integrated Pest Management (IPM) is an ecological form of pest management that emerged in the United States in the 1950s in response to the pesticide crisis and now informs numerous pesticide legislations around the world (Wolff, L., 2023). IPM principles were first introduced by Stern et al. (1959). The FAO has defined² IPM as the “careful consideration of all available pest control techniques and subsequent integration of appropriate measures that discourage the development of pest populations and keep pesticides and other interventions to levels that are economically justified and reduce or minimize risks to human health and the environment.”

In the EU legislation, the IPM is defined in the Sustainable Use of Pesticides Directive (SUD)³. According to the Directive the integrated pest management means careful consideration of all available plant protection methods and subsequent integration of appropriate measures that discourage the development of populations of harmful organisms and keep the use of plant protection products and other forms of intervention to levels that are economically and ecologically justified and reduce or minimise risks to human health and the environment. IPM emphasises the growth of a healthy crop with the least possible disruption to agro-ecosystems and encourages natural pest control mechanisms. In the Annex III of the SUD, a more operational translation of IPM is provided by laying out eight general principles. Namely, (i) prevention and suppression, (ii) monitoring, (iii) decision-making, (iv) non-chemical methods, (v) pesticide selection, (vi) reduced pesticide use, (vii) anti-resistance strategies, and (viii) evaluation. Sound

² [FAO definition for IPM](#)

³ [Directive 2009/128/EC](#) of the European Parliament and of the Council of 21 October 2009 establishing a framework for Community action to achieve the sustainable use of pesticides, OJ L 309, 24.11.2009, p. 71–86.

IPM is a knowledge-demanding and context-specific systems approach, which consequently utilizes a wide range of tools and technologies (Barzman et al., 2015; Göldel et al., 2020; Veres et al., 2020). Hence, crop protection is more and more acknowledged to be more nuanced than an exclusive reliance on pesticides, and particularly chemical pesticides (Council Decision (EU) 2022/2572).

Eight general principles of integrated pest management – A mandatory practice to be followed to reduce the risks of pesticide use (Annex III, SUD)

1. The prevention and/or suppression of harmful organisms should be achieved or supported among other options, especially by **crop rotation**; use of adequate cultivation techniques; use, where appropriate, of resistant/tolerant cultivars and standard/certified seed and planting material; use of balanced fertilisation, liming and irrigation/drainage practices; preventing the spreading of harmful organisms by hygiene measures; protection and enhancement of important beneficial organisms.
2. Harmful organisms must be **monitored** by adequate methods and tools, where available. Such adequate tools should include observations in the field as well as scientifically sound warning, forecasting and early diagnosis systems, where feasible, as well as the use of advice from professionally qualified **advisors**.
3. Based on the results of the monitoring, the professional user has to decide whether and when to apply plant protection measures. Robust and scientifically sound **threshold values** are essential components for decision making. For harmful organisms, threshold levels defined for the region, specific areas, crops and particular climatic conditions must be taken into account before treatments, where feasible.
4. **Sustainable biological, physical and other non-chemical methods** must be preferred to chemical methods if they provide satisfactory pest control.
5. The pesticides applied shall be as **specific** as possible for the target and shall have the least side effects on human health, non-target organisms and the environment.
6. The professional user should keep the use of pesticides and other forms of intervention to **levels that are necessary**, e.g. by reduced doses, reduced application frequency or partial applications, considering that the level of risk in vegetation is acceptable and they do not increase the risk for development of resistance in populations of harmful organisms.
7. Where the risk of resistance against a plant protection measure is known and where the level of harmful organisms requires repeated application of pesticides to the crops, available **anti-resistance strategies** should be applied to maintain the effectiveness of the products. This may include the use of multiple pesticides with different modes of action.
8. Based on the records on the use of pesticides and on the monitoring of harmful organisms, the professional user should check the success of the applied plant protection measures.

The eight principles and their numbering actually result from a logical sequence of events. **Figure 1** illustrates this sequence. Principle 1 (Prevention and suppression) comes first because it encompasses the initial design and actions undertaken at the cropping system level to reduce the severity and frequency of pest outbreaks. Principles 2 (Monitoring) and 3 (Decision-making), which come into play once the cropping system is in place, are based on the idea that inseason

control measures result from a sound decision making process that takes into account actual or predicted pest incidence. In the event that an intervention is decided, Principles 4 to 7 offer a sequence of control options that can be explored starting with the least preoccupying ones first. Principle 8 (Evaluation) closes the loop by ensuring that users look back and assess their actions in view of improving the entire process (Barzman et al., 2015).

The most important element of IPM is **prevention**. The farmer uses a host of different strategies to prevent pest build-up using appropriate crop cultivation methods.

Figure 2: [CropLife Europe, "What is IPM?", 2021.](#)

Then we have **observation** of the crop – farmers need to monitor pest levels. Farmers need to continuously monitor their crops in case any control measures need to be deployed. Lastly we have **intervention**. Before any chemical control is considered – all physical, mechanical and biological options are explored. For example, alyssum flowers added to an agroecosystem can increase the abundance and efficiency of syrphid flies that can lead to lower aphid numbers. It's important to remember that chemical control is considered as a last resort. In fact, it is only advised when all other strategies have been considered as not viable. Pesticides should be used as much as necessary and as little as possible. The principle of effective IPM is to develop pest control strategies that take into account all locally relevant control tactics and methods. This means understanding and working with the local environment and its specific needs.

An important role in IPM is played by biological control: the use of natural enemies against pests and diseases. This can be done by the one-off release of natural enemies against invasive pests (classical biological control), the repetitive release of insects or micro-organisms against recurring pests (augmentative biological control) or the protection of the elements in the agroecosystem in which naturally occurring beneficial insects occur (conservation biological control). IPM emphasises the growth of a healthy crop with the least possible disruption to agroecosystems and encourages natural pest control mechanisms and uses chemical control only

when all other control means are exhausted.

In the public consultation conducted during the impact assessment of the SUR proposal, more tailored IPM guidance was viewed as positive by pesticide users and industry (110 out of 151) as well as non-governmental organisations (NGOs) and civil society organisations (21 out of 22). Product-specific information on which pesticides may best complement holistic IPM schemes could be useful (Böckmann et al., 2019). The impact assessment also found current implementation of IPM to be at sub-optimal levels. Supporting better uptake, however, could play a major role in reducing pesticide use and risk as IPM limits the use of chemical pesticides as a last resort.

In this respect, sharing the extensive information on IPM approaches developed for years is key for the uptake of IPM by the farming community and beyond. This was the purpose in particular of the pilot project 'Farmer's Toolbox for Integrated Pest Management' conducted between December 2020 and November 2022 in which over 1300 IPM strategies and over 270 crop-specific guidelines from 24 EU countries were identified and made available in a common database. The conclusions show that most of the guidelines can be directly used by farmers (72 %) and more than half (53 %) are used by authorities for controlling the implementation of IPM by farmers. Around 96 % of Member States have guidelines on arable crops, followed by fruits and vegetables, viticulture, and other crops. From the 273 crop-specific guidelines in EU countries, 145 guidelines are used by authorities for controlling the current implementation of IPM by farmers.

3.2 IPM-related policies at EU level

The **European Green Deal**⁴ (EGD), which proposes to achieve a climate-neutral Europe by 2050, puts a strong focus on the transition to a more sustainable agriculture and food system and states that all EU policies should contribute to preserving and restoring Europe's natural capital⁵. In particular, the EGD aims to significantly reduce the use and risk of chemical pesticides in general, and the use of more hazardous pesticides in particular. In the **Farm to Fork Strategy**⁶, **Biodiversity Strategy**⁷, the **Zero Pollution**⁸ **Action Plan** and the **Soil Strategy**,⁹ the Commission committed to take action to reduce by 50% the overall use of and risk from chemical pesticides by 2030 and reduce by 50% the use of more hazardous pesticides by 2030. The Commission's communication on the Farm to Fork strategy, published in May 2020, aims to address priorities and challenges in the food system by bringing sustainability to the heart of each step of the food chain, calling upon all relevant stakeholders to contribute to this objective. It highlights that there is an urgent need to reduce the dependency on pesticides and that it will enhance provisions on integrated pest management (IPM).

In its **Resolution**¹⁰ **on the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030**, the European Parliament welcomed the Commission's targets of reducing the use of more hazardous and chemical pesticides by 50 %, and called for an effective assessment of these targets on the basis of specific milestones;

In its **Resolution**¹¹ **on the Farm to Fork Strategy**, the European Parliament emphasised the importance of taking action to promote sustainable farming and reduce the use of pesticides and the associated risks. The Members of the Parliament (MEPs) welcomed the decision to revise the directive on the sustainable use of pesticides and the reduction targets for pesticide use. Nevertheless, it's noteworthy that the resolution did not specify concrete reduction targets for pesticide use. Instead, it highlighted that the attainability of these goals hinges on the accessibility of safer, more effective,

⁴ Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the European Council, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions **The European Green Deal** COM/2019/640 final, [EUR-Lex - 52019DC0640 - EN - EUR-Lex \(europa.eu\)](#)

⁵ EU guidelines [SWD \(2019\)305](#) FINAL "EU guidance on integrating ecosystems and their services into decision-making"

⁶ Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee Of The Regions, [A Farm to Fork Strategy](#) for a fair, healthy and environmentally-friendly food system, COM/2020/381 final.

⁷ Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee Of The Regions [EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 Bringing nature back into our lives](#), COM/2020/380 final.

⁸ Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee Of The Regions, [Pathway to a Healthy Planet for All](#) EU Action Plan: 'Towards Zero Pollution for Air, Water and Soil', COM(2021) 400 final.

⁹ Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee Of The Regions, [EU Soil Strategy for 2030](#) Reaping the benefits of healthy soils for people, food, nature and climate, COM(2021) 699 final.

¹⁰ *European Parliament resolution of 9 June 2021 on the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030: Bringing nature back into our lives* ([2020/2273\(INI\)](#)).

¹¹ *European Parliament resolution of 20 October 2021 on a farm to fork strategy for a fair, healthy and environmentally-friendly food system* ([2020/2260\(INI\)](#))

and efficient alternatives. The EP, in its resolution, stressed the key role of IPM in reducing pesticide dependency and urged the Member States to ensure it is applied and that its implementation is assessed and monitored systematically. It also called on the Member States to convert the general IPM principles into practical and measurable criteria and to verify these criteria at farm level, and on the Commission to ensure that Member States effectively implement these IPM principles through their CAP strategic plans.

In its **Resolution¹² on ensuring food security** and long-term resilience of the EU agriculture, the European Parliament underlines that agri-environmental-climate practices, such as agroecology, agroforestry, integrated pest management (IPM), organic farming, precision and carbon farming, have the potential to address climate, biodiversity, environmental, economic and social challenges. The Resolution also emphasizes the key role of IPM in reducing pesticide dependency and urges the Member States to ensure its proper application. Additionally, it calls on the Commission to provide financial and other forms of support to assist farmers in transitioning to IPM and agri-environmental-climate practices. Nevertheless, MEPs express concerns that further restrictions on the availability of plant protection products could potentially undermine the progress made in implementing the holistic approach of IPM.

In its **Conclusions¹³ on the Farm to Fork Strategy**, approved on October 19, 2020, the Council took note of the reduction targets for pesticides, antimicrobials and fertilisers as well as the other targets set out in the F2F Strategy, without referring to specific numerical targets and pointed out that achieving those targets would require efforts from Member States and all stakeholders and intensive co-operation, consultation and collaboration. The Council called on the Commission to support the development of more comprehensive plant protection approaches based on the principles of integrated pest management, highlighting in this regard the importance of ensuring adequate and scientifically-sound IPM measures and the promotion of the use of sustainable alternative plant protection products and methods.

The authorisation and marketing of pesticides have been regulated at the EU level since 1991. The EU operates one of the most rigorous systems globally for authorizing and overseeing the use of pesticides, if not the most stringent. Directive 2009/128/EC¹⁴ on the sustainable use of pesticides (the SUD), Regulation (EC) No 1107/2009¹⁵, Regulation (EC) No 396/2005¹⁶, Regulation (EU)

¹² *European Parliament resolution of 14 June 2023 on ensuring food security and long term resilience of the EU agriculture (2022/2183(INI))*

¹³ *Council [Conclusions](#) on the Farm to Fork Strategy (12099/20).*

¹⁴ Directive 2009/128/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 21 October 2009 establishing a framework for Community action to achieve the sustainable use of pesticides, OJ L 309, 24.11.2009, p. 71–86.

¹⁵ Regulation (EC) No 1107/2009 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 21 October 2009 concerning the placing of plant protection products on the market and repealing Council Directives 79/117/EEC and 91/414/EEC, OJ L 309, 24.11.2009, p. 1–50.

¹⁶ Regulation (EC) No 396/2005 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 February 2005 on maximum residue levels of pesticides in or on food and feed of plant and animal origin and amending Council Directive 91/414/EEC, OJ L 70, 16.3.2005, p. 1–16.

2017/625¹⁷, Regulation (EU) 2021/2115¹⁸, Regulation (EU) 2022/2379¹⁹, Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2023/564²⁰ and Regulation (EU) 2023/.....²¹ provide a legislative basis for the safe and sustainable use of pesticides in the European Union.

The year 2006 marked a major development of the EU pesticides policy. In particular, the European Commission published a communication²² on a thematic strategy on the sustainable use of pesticides. Its purpose was to fill in certain gaps in the policy framework, especially as regards the use of pesticides. The strategy envisaged legislative and non-legislative policy measures whose implementation was expected to reduce the risks and negative impact on human health and the environment provoked by the use of pesticides. The EC started several initiatives to support Member States in the implementation of IPM. A series of Better Training for Safer Food (BTSF) trainings on the implementation of IPM were funded to generate an understanding of the holistic approach of IPM, promote increase on-farm implementation of IPM as well stimulate the development of criteria for IPM implementation.

The strategy led to the adoption of the **Sustainable Use of Pesticides Directive (SUD)**²³ in 2009. The SUD aims to achieve a sustainable use of pesticides by reducing the risks and impacts of pesticide use on human health and the environment and promoting the use of integrated pest management (IPM) and of alternative approaches or techniques, such as non chemical alternatives to pesticides. In fact, the promotion of IPM is a cornerstone of the SUD, for which general principles are laid down in Annex III to the Directive. Along with the promotion of organic farming, IPM is one of the tools for low-pesticide-input pest management, and IPM must be implemented by all professional users. The directive also envisages the establishment of harmonised risk indicators

¹⁷ Regulation (EU) 2017/625 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 15 March 2017 on official controls and other official activities performed to ensure the application of food and feed law, rules on animal health and welfare, plant health and plant protection products, amending Regulations (EC) No 999/2001, (EC) No 396/2005, (EC) No 1069/2009, (EC) No 1107/2009, (EU) No 1151/2012, (EU) No 652/2014, (EU) 2016/429 and (EU) 2016/2031 of the European Parliament and of the Council, Council Regulations (EC) No 1/2005 and (EC) No 1099/2009 and Council Directives 98/58/EC, 1999/74/EC, 2007/43/EC, 2008/119/EC and 2008/120/EC, and repealing Regulations (EC) No 854/2004 and (EC) No 882/2004 of the European Parliament and of the Council, Council Directives 89/608/EEC, 89/662/EEC, 90/425/EEC, 91/496/EEC, 96/23/EC, 96/93/EC and 97/78/EC and Council Decision 92/438/EEC (Official Controls Regulation), OJ L 95, 7.4.2017, p. 1–142.

¹⁸ [Regulation \(EU\) 2021/2115](#) of the European Parliament and of the Council of 2 December 2021 establishing rules on support for strategic plans to be drawn up by Member States under the common agricultural policy (CAP Strategic Plans) and financed by the European Agricultural Guarantee Fund (EAGF) and by the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD) and repealing Regulations (EU) No 1305/2013 and (EU) No 1307/2013, OJ L 435, 6.12.2021

¹⁹ [Regulation \(EU\) 2022/2379](#) concerning the statistics on agricultural input and output, amending Commission Regulation (EC) No 617/2008 and repealing Regulations (EC) No 1165/2008, (EC) No 543/2009 and (EC) No 1185/2009 of the European Parliament and of the Council and Council Directive 96/16/EC

²⁰ [Commission Implementing Regulation \(EU\) 2023/564](#) of 10 March 2023 as regards the content and format of the records of plant protection products kept by professional users pursuant to Regulation (EC) No 1107/2009 of the European Parliament and of the Council.

²¹ Regulation (EU) No ... of the European Parliament and of the Council of xx xx 2023 amending Council Regulation (EC) No 1217/2009 as regards conversion of the Farm Accountancy Data Network into a Farm Sustainability Data Network.

²² [Communication](#) from the Commission to the Council, the European Parliament, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions - A thematic strategy on the sustainable use of pesticides {COM(2006) 373 final} {SEC(2006) 894} {SEC(2006) 895} {SEC(2006) 914}.

²³ [Directive 2009/128/EC](#) of the European Parliament and of the Council of 21 October 2009 establishing a framework for Community action to achieve the sustainable use of pesticides, OJ L 309, 24.11.2009, p. 71–86.

(HRIs) to estimate the trends in risks associated with pesticides. The Commission established two such indicators – HRI 1 and HRI 2 – for the first time in May 2019; they referred to the period 2011-2017.⁴ In August 2021, the Commission updated the HRIs to refer to the period 2011-2019. Member States were required to bring into force the national provisions of transposing the SUD by 26 November 2011. The implementation of the SUD is closely interlinked with the EU legislative framework regulating pesticides that are PPPs and its implementation.

In June 2022, the Commission published its **proposal²⁴ for a new Regulation on the sustainable use of plant protection products (SUR)** to replace the SUD. According to the Commission work programme for 2022, this was initially expected on 23 March 2022, but it was delayed, reportedly, as a result of Russia's war on Ukraine (EPRS, 2022). The proposal is part of a package on nature protection and it is designed to address four problems: 1) alignment with pesticide-related targets in the F2F Strategy; 2) strengthening current SUD provisions; 3) improving data availability and monitoring; and 4) addressing new technologies. The proposal contains many of the provisions of the SUD but also sets legally binding reduction targets - to be achieved collectively by the Member States by 2030 – which refer to both the risk and use of pesticides, tightens the provision for pesticide-free areas, and more clearly defines what an IPM is and how it can be assessed. This is a major difference from the current SUD, which only aims to reduce the risks from the use of pesticides but does not have as an explicit objective a reduction in the use of pesticides. To support the transition towards an ambitious reduction in the use of pesticides, the Commission has proposed a derogation to allow additional funding, through the CAP Funds (by amending Regulation (EU) 2021/2115), for implementing obligations resulting from the SUR Regulation – even if normally required as SMRs or GAECs (thus in the baseline) – during a period of 5 years after its entry into force. Member States may thus, if the SUR Regulation were adopted as proposed, choose to provide additional funding for these practices related to pesticide reduction. A significant feature of the proposal for revision is the upgrade of the directive to a regulation, i.e., it would be directly applicable in its entirety in all Member States, and therefore seeks uniform implementation of the EU rules at national level.

The report adopted on 24 October 2023 by the EP's ENVI committee supports an EU-wide reduction of at least 50 % in the use and risk of chemical PPPs and raises the reduction goal for the use of more hazardous ones to 65 % by 2030. It extends the baseline period for calculating progress towards these targets. To increase the availability and use of alternative solutions, the report requires the setting of an additional EU-wide 2030 target for increasing overall sales of low-risk PPPs and biological control, and introduces measures to accelerate market access for such products. However, the European Parliament rejected the Commission's proposal during the Plenary sitting on November 22nd, 2023 following a tense voting session and closed its first reading²⁵. The proposal is still (December 2023) under discussion in the Council. For many delegations, the most difficult aspects of the proposal remain the mandatory reduction targets at national level, and the prohibition on the use of plant protection products in sensitive areas. The Spanish Presidency prepared a Presidency compromise text for the whole proposal in November 2023, seeking to bridge the divergent views and positions expressed by the delegations in the previous meetings.

The main piece of EU pesticides legislation relevant to the SUD and its implementation is **Regulation**

²⁴ [Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on the sustainable use of plant protection products and amending Regulation \(EU\) 2021/2115.](#)

²⁵ [European Parliament legislative resolution of 22 November 2023 on the proposal for a regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on the sustainable use of plant protection products and amending Regulation \(EU\) 2021/2115 \(COM\(2022\)0305 – C9-0207/2022 – 2022/0196\(COD\)\).](#)

(EC) No 1107/2009²⁶ concerning the placing of plant protection products (PPPs) on the market (the 'PPP Regulation'). It governs the approval of active substances²⁷ and the authorisation of PPPs containing or consisting of such substances. In particular, the approval of active substances is done at EU level by the Commission, based on a two-step approach: the first step is a 'hazard assessment' (against a set of 'cut-off' criteria defined by the same regulation) performed by the Member State(s) acting as (a) rapporteur(s); the second step is a 'risk assessment' performed by the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA). After EFSA has published its Conclusion, the European Commission decides whether or not to include the substance in the EU's list of approved active substances. This determines whether the substance can be used in plant protection products in the EU. Member States assess or re-assess the safety of plant protection products containing the active substance that are sold in their territory. Article 53 of the PPP Regulation allows Member States to grant emergency authorisation for the use of non-authorised PPPs in exceptional circumstances and for a limited period of time.

The use of plant protection products by professional users should be recorded in line with Article 67 of Regulation (EC) No 1107/2009²⁸, containing the name of the product, the time and the dose of application, the area treated and the crop where the product was used. **Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2023/564**²⁹ regards the content and format of these records. From January 2026, the records should be kept electronically to enable a uniform application of the record-keeping obligation. This ensures greater reliability of the records, facilitates their collection and verification by the competent authorities and ultimately supports accurate, efficient and effective monitoring and control activities by Member States. Professional users should have sufficient time between recording of each use of plant protection products and the transfer of the records into electronic format. The records shall be transferred into such a format no later than 30 days from the date of use of the plant protection product. For use of plant protection products on their territory before 1 January 2030, Member States may allow for longer periods than 30 days, as long as all records are available in the prescribed electronic format before 31 January of the year following the year of use of the plant protection product.

Regulation (EU) 2022/2379³⁰ (the SAIO Regulation) establishes an integrated framework for aggregated European statistics on agricultural inputs and products, as well as on their intermediate use in agriculture, their collection and processing. It will also cover statistics on the sale and use of plant protection products, broken down by active substance. For the detailed topic of use of plant protection products in agriculture, a transitional period of three years from 2025 has been agreed, with an intermediate data collection for the reference year 2026. From base year 2028 onwards, data collection will be annual with annual publication from 2030 onwards. The collection of PPP data will be based on a common list of representative crops, which will evolve during the transition period. This common part shall cover, together with permanent grassland, at least 75% of the total utilised

²⁶ [Regulation \(EC\) No 1107/2009](#) of the European Parliament and of the Council of 21 October 2009 concerning the placing of plant protection products on the market and repealing Council Directives 79/117/EEC and 91/414/EEC.

²⁷ An active substance is any chemical, plant extract, pheromone or micro-organism (including viruses), that has action against 'pests' or on plants, parts of plants or plant products.

²⁸ [Regulation \(EC\) No 1107/2009](#), concerning the placing of plant protection products on the market and repealing Council Directives 79/117/EEC and 91/414/EEC, OJ L 309, 24.11.2009, p. 1–50.

²⁹ [Commission Implementing Regulation \(EU\) 2023/564](#) of 10 March 2023 as regards the content and format of the records of plant protection products kept by professional users pursuant to Regulation (EC) No 1107/2009 of the European Parliament and of the Council.

³⁰ [Regulation \(EU\) 2022/2379](#) concerning the statistics on agricultural input and output, amending Commission Regulation (EC) No 617/2008 and repealing Regulations (EC) No 1165/2008, (EC) No 543/2009 and (EC) No 1185/2009 of the European Parliament and of the Council and Council Directive 96/16/EC

agricultural area at Union level. The coverage of agricultural use will be increased to 95% from the reference year following the date of entry into force of the Union legislation requiring professional users of plant protection products to submit their records on the use of these products to the national competent authorities in electronic format (Register). In this regard, Parliament and the Council made a joint statement.

Regulation (EU) 2023/2674³¹ (the FSDN Regulation) regards the conversion of the Farm Accountancy Data Network (FADN) into a Farm Sustainability Data Network (FSDN), aiming to collect farm level data on sustainability. The conversion will also contribute to the improvement of advisory services to farmers and benchmarking of farm performance. Based on the well-established FADN data network, the FSDN will be a useful and efficient tool that enables the EU to contribute to the CAP and Farm to Fork objectives and make available farm level economic, environmental and social data and information for the Member States as well as the EU. Like the FADN, the FSDN will provide a common and harmonised survey to collect farm level data and make data comparable at EU level. The economic, environmental and social data categories to be collected are set out in an Annex and under this list of topics, data will be collected about both the use of plant protection products and farming practices, such as integrated pest management.

All matters related to legal limits for pesticide residues in food and feed are covered by **Regulation (EC) No 396/2005**³² that sets up maximum residue levels of pesticides in or on food and feed of plant and animal origin. The machinery for plant protection products application is regulated by **Regulation (EU) 2023/1230**³³ and by **Directive 2009/127/EC**³⁴. Another relevant piece of EU law is **Regulation (EU) 2017/625**³⁵ on official controls performed to ensure the application of food and feed law, which directly concerns PPPs and their use.

The **Regulation (EU) 2021/2115**³⁶ (The CAP Regulation), establishing rules on support for strategic plans to be drawn up by Member States under the common agricultural policy, includes several tools aiming to support the F2F and Biodiversity strategies objectives, meaning the reduction of pesticides use and risk. The CAP Regulation includes the scope for Member States to promote specific sustainable farming practices, such as organic farming, IPM, agro-ecology, agroforestry or precision farming, in order to improve the response to societal demands on food and health, including high-quality, safe, and nutritious food produced in a sustainable way. It also includes provisions for the Member States to set a strong mandatory baseline of requirements that make up the basis for IPM in both Statutory Management Requirements (SMRs) and the Good Agricultural and

³¹ [REGULATION \(EU\) No 2023/2674](#), amending Council Regulation (EC) No 1217/2009 as regards conversion of the Farm Accountancy Data Network into a Farm Sustainability Data Network, OJ L, 2023/2674, 29.11.2023.

³² [Regulation \(EC\) No 396/2005](#) of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 February 2005 on maximum residue levels of pesticides in or on food and feed of plant and animal origin and amending Council Directive 91/414/EEC.

³³ [Regulation \(EU\) 2023/1230](#) on machinery and repealing Directive 2006/42/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council and Council Directive 73/361/EEC

³⁴ [Directive 2009/127/EC](#) of the European Parliament and of the Council of 21 October 2009 amending Directive 2006/42/EC with regard to machinery for pesticide application.

³⁵ [Regulation \(EU\) 2017/625](#) of the European Parliament and of the Council of 15 March 2017 on official controls and other official activities performed to ensure the application of food and feed law, rules on animal health and welfare, plant health and plant protection products (...).

³⁶ [Regulation \(EU\) 2021/2115](#) of the European Parliament and of the Council of 2 December 2021 establishing rules on support for strategic plans to be drawn up by Member States under the common agricultural policy (CAP Strategic Plans) and financed by the European Agricultural Guarantee Fund (EAGF) and by the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD) and repealing Regulations (EU) No 1305/2013 and (EU) No 1307/2013, OJ L 435, 6.12.2021

Environmental Conditions (GAEC) for crop rotation, buffer strips along water courses, cover crops, and at least 4% of area under landscape features and fallow or nitrogen-fixing crops in which pesticides are not used. Building on the previous system of cross-compliance implemented until 2022, the system of new conditionality links full receipt of CAP support to the compliance of farmers and other beneficiaries with basic standards concerning the environment, climate change, public health, plant health and animal welfare. The basic standards encompass in a streamlined form a list of statutory management requirements (SMRs) and standards of good agricultural and environmental conditions of land (GAEC standards). SMR 8 is the SUD³⁷ and the GAECs 4 (Establishment of buffer strips along water courses) and 7 (Crop rotation in arable land, except for crops growing under water) are directly related to the IPM. The rest of the GAECs may have an indirect impact on IPM uptake and the reductions of risk and use of plant protection products because they have the potential to impact agronomic practices and therefore can be considered as IPM measures. Schemes for the climate, the environment and animal welfare (Eco-schemes/Art. 31), environmental, climate-related and other management commitments (ECC/Art. 70) and investments in the fruit and vegetables sector, the hops sector, the olive oil and table olives sector and the wine sector can then be used to provide incentives for farmers to apply IPM or to carry out practices that support IPM. Another important tool of the CAP Regulation are the farm advisory services (FAS/Art. 15). Member States should integrate all public and private advisors and advisory networks within the Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems (AKIS). Farm advisory services should help farmers and other beneficiaries of CAP support to become more aware of the relationship between farm management and land management on the one hand, and certain standards, requirements and information, including environmental and climate ones, on the other hand, such as those stemming from the legislation on the sustainable use of pesticide.

³⁷ Specifically Article 5(2) and Article 8(1) to (5); Article 12 with regard to restrictions on the use of pesticides in protected areas defined on the basis of Directive 2000/60/EC and Natura 2000 legislation; Article 13(1) and (3) on handling and storage of pesticides and disposal of remnants.

3.3. IPM-related policies at national level

3.3.1 National Action Plans

The SUD is largely based on actions to be taken at Member State level, given the variation in agriculture across the EU. It requires Member States to produce National Action Plans (NAPs) setting out how they will achieve the sustainable use of pesticides, including quantitative objectives, targets, measures and timetables to reduce the risks and impacts of pesticide use on human health and the environment. This should include indicators to monitor the use of pesticides containing active substances of particular concern.

Objectives and targets established by MSs in the NAPs

In 2017 the Commission³⁸ (COM(2017)587) encouraged Member States to review and improve the quality of their NAPs, by establishing specific and measurable targets and indicators at national level, which they had been required to do in the SUD. These targets would then allow Member States to monitor progress in the implementation of the SUD, and to adjust their strategy where necessary.

More than two thirds of Member States failed to complete the review of their initial NAP within the five-year legal deadline (COM(2020)204)³⁹. Belgium, Denmark, France, Germany, Poland and Spain concluded the review of their initial NAP within the five-year deadline (2018). Germany did not make any substantial changes, as it considered that there was sufficient flexibility in their initial NAP, while Italy's NAP dates back to 2012. Romania submitted its reviewed NAP in 2019 and Greece in 2020. Denmark (2022), Netherlands (2022) and Spain (2023) have recently reviewed their NAPs.

Only a small minority of Member States identified specific examples of useful targets and indicators based on the review of their initial NAPs. Denmark, France and Germany identified useful targets based on a review of their initial NAPs. Germany established a target of a 30% reduction in potential risk to the environment by 2023 compared to a baseline of the average for 1996-2005. The Danish Pesticides Strategy 2017-2021 had an objective of a Pesticide Load Indicator (PLI) of no more than 1.96 (based on sales figures), corresponding to a 40% reduction compared with the calculated level in 2011. In order to achieve record-low plant protection products load, Denmark set the PLI target of 1.43 based on sales figures for 2025 in its revised NAP 2022-2026. This gives a further reduction of 27% and will be evaluated in 2026. Finally, France set a target for a 25% reduction in PPP use by 2020, and a 50% reduction in use by 2025, compared to 2015, without having a negative impact on farm incomes.

Most Member States have not addressed the weaknesses identified by the Commission in their initial NAPs in their revised NAPs, so that the majority of revised NAPs lack ambition and fail to define high-level, outcome-based targets, so as to reduce the risks associated with, and dependency on PPPs (COM(2020)204). Austria, Belgium, Denmark, Poland and Spain revised NAPs focus on reducing risk, while France focus on overall use reduction as a means of reducing risk.

³⁸ Report from the Commission to the European Parliament and the Council on Member State National Action Plans and on progress in the implementation of Directive 2009/128/EC on the sustainable use of pesticides, COM(2017)587.

³⁹ Report from the Commission to the European Parliament and the Council on the experience gained by Member States on the implementation of national targets established in their National Action Plans and on progress in the implementation of Directive 2009/128/EC on the sustainable use of pesticides, COM(2020)204.

Other Member States have either action-based, or compliance-based, targets. Poland has established an indicator⁴⁰, based on compliance levels with specific aspects of Regulation (EC) No 1107/2009, e.g. use of authorised PPPs, and the SUD, e.g. compliance with the requirement for professional users to be trained, and sets a high-level target based on the output of this indicator. Spain and Belgium both set clear targets, but all are sector-specific and relate to actions, e.g. the number of information campaigns/year, or the number of demonstration farms to be established, rather than quantifiable impacts, e.g. the number of professional users implementing IPM (COM(2020)204).

Among the SUPPORT countries Belgium, Denmark, France, Germany and Greece have included quantitative objectives and targets in their NAPs, Italy has established a quantitative target which is not integrated yet in the NAP that dates back to 2012 and the rest have included mainly qualitative targets (**Table 1**).

Table 1: Objectives and targets established by MSs in the NAPs

Member State	Description of the objectives and targets
Belgium	Walloon plan: 50% reduction in the environmental impact for non-agricultural use. 25% reduction in the environmental impact of agricultural use.
Denmark	The Pesticide Load Indicator (PLI) sets a more ambitious target of 1.43 based on sales figures for 2025, instead of the previous one of 1.96. The previous target aimed to reduce sales by 40% of the figure for 2011 sales. The new one gives a further reduction of 27%. This will be evaluated in 2026. The PPPs tax will be restructured to make it more attractive to use plant protection products with low loads on the environment and health.
France	50% reduction of pesticide use by 2025.
Germany	DE sets quantitative targets for risk reduction of 20% by 2018 and by 30% by 2020.
Greece	2.5% reduction of HRI 2 per year; 5% increase of low-risk products (Art.47 of Reg (EC) No 1107/2009) per year; 2% increase of products containing micro-organisms per year; 2% reduction of the percentage of exceedances in the food and feed residue monitoring programmes (national and Community) per year.
Netherlands	Mainly qualitative targets. Quantitative targets aim to achieve virtually no emissions of plant protection products from outdoor cultivation into the environment (see below).

⁴⁰ Available at:

https://ec.europa.eu/food/sites/food/files/plant/docs/pesticides_sup_nap_pol-rev-2018_en.pdf

Romania	The 2019 revised NAP includes generic objectives only and the specific objectives follow the requirements of the SUD provisions article per article.
Spain	Mainly qualitative targets (see below).
Poland	The level of irregularities related to the use of PPPs should not exceed 1.5, over the course of delivery of the NAP 2018-2022.

Source: Farmer's toolbox for IPM⁴¹, updated by AUA.

The recently revised National Action Plan of the **Netherlands**⁴² aligns with the Dutch policy for plant protection in agriculture from 2020 to 2030, as defined in the Implementation Programme for the Vision for the Future of Plant Protection 2030. This program includes objectives and actions to make plants and cultivation systems resilient. In 2022, new policy intentions were introduced focusing on integrated pest management, aligning plant protection product standards with the Water Framework Directive, and conducting health research for farmers and residents. The National Action Plan complements this policy, addressing aspects not covered in the previous policy, such as professional competence, inspections of plant protection equipment, professional use outside agriculture, and private use. The plan has a four-year term instead of five. Potential policy changes, actions in the Implementation Programme, the new SAIO regulation on agricultural statistics and potential amendments to the SUD may require adjustments. Despite these factors, the plan was adopted due to legal requirements, with any necessary changes addressed before the next plan in 2026.

In **Table 2**, the objectives, measures and targets to reduce risks and effects of plant protection products on human health and the environment and encourage IPM, are listed. The purpose of these actions is to strengthen the further development and application of principles of integrated pest management aimed at preventive and non-chemical measures, monitoring diseases, pests and weeds, and applying plant protection products as specifically as possible (precision agriculture). For the purposes of reducing exceedances of water quality standards, quantitative targets have been formulated in order to achieve the objectives under the Water Framework Directive for surface water, drinking water and groundwater by 2027, with the ultimate objective being to have virtually no emissions of plant protection products from outdoor cultivation into the environment. The rest of the targets are qualitative.

⁴¹ European Commission, Directorate-General for Agriculture and Rural Development, *Farmer's toolbox for integrated pest management – Executive summary*, Publications Office of the European Union, 2023, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2762/508855>

⁴² [Updated Dutch National Action Plan on the sustainable use of plant protection products 2022-2025](#)

Table 2: Strategic and Interim Objectives of the updated Dutch National Action Plan on the sustainable use of plant protection products 2022-2025.

Strategic objectives	Plant and cultivation systems are resilient			Agriculture and horticulture are connected with nature			Virtually no emissions and residues		
	2021	2022	2023-2030	2021	2025	2030	2023	2027	2030
Interim objectives	A toolkit is available to farmers at farm level that provides insight into feasible courses of action to strengthen the resilience of plants and cultivation systems.	A baseline measurement is in place of the feasible courses of actions available to create resilience in each sector, and of the environmental impact of PPPs within resilient cultivation systems in each sector.	In each sector, a downward trend is evident in the environmental impact of plant protection products as a result of the (continued) development of resilient cultivation systems.	There is insight into the connection between plant-based production, plant protection and biodiversity. Indicators for this are applied as prototypes in practice.	Cost-effective measures that strengthen both the resilience of the cultivation system and biodiversity are being applied in the relevant regions, sectors and types of cultivation and these measures are valued by the agricultural chain.	Cost-effective measures that strengthen both the resilience of the cultivation system and biodiversity are standard practice and these measures are valued in the agricultural chain, also internationally.	90% reduction compared to 2013 of the number of exceedances of maximum concentrations for PPP residues in surface water applying under the environmental water quality standards;	virtually no emissions of PPPs from farmyards and buildings when filling and surface cleaning spraying equipment and from greenhouse horticulture;	Virtually no emissions of PPPs from open-field cultivation.
	A toolkit is available that provides insight into the environmental impact of plant protection products within resilient cultivation systems.						95% reduction compared to 2013 of the number of exceedances of maximum concentrations for PPP residues in surface water applying under the quality standard for surface water intended for drinking water preparation.	no exceedances of maximum concentrations for plant protection product residues in surface water applying under the environmental water quality standards;	
								In addition, the objectives for 2027 under the Water Framework Directive apply. The principle under the Implementation Programme is that these objectives are to be achieved.	
							Virtually no residues in agriculture and horticulture products intended for food consumption	Virtually no residues in agriculture and horticulture products intended for food consumption	Virtually no residues in agriculture and horticulture products intended for food consumption.

Source: Compiled by AUA based on the analysis of the NAPs and completed by interviews with the NCAs

In Spain, the new NAP 2023-2024 on the sustainable use of PPPs aims to promote IPM and reduce the risks and effects derived from the use of phytosanitary products on human health and the environment. It requires, for example, publishing data on risk indicators, improving information, reinforcing market surveillance of phytosanitary products, limiting their use in protected areas or promoting innovation through the support of operating groups within the national strategic plan of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP).

The general objectives of the recently revised **Spanish NAP 2023-2024**⁴³ are as follows:

1. To promote integrated pest management (IPM) to ensure the farming, forestry and food sector remains prosperous and to make a positive contribution to the environment through a sustainable production model that is compatible with the rational use of plant protection products.
2. To reduce the risks and effects related to the use of plant protection products, especially in the field of human health and the environment.

Specific priority objectives, in the form of measures or groups of measures, are provided to ensure achievement of the general objectives. In **Table 3** the main targets set per each specific priority objective, are listed.

Table 3: Main targets set per each specific priority objective of the updated Spanish NAP 2023-2024.

SPAIN - NAP's Specific Objectives	Improve training and information on the sustainable and safe use of PPPs	Promote innovation and technology transfer in IPM and the sustainable use of PPPs	Promote IPM to ensure a rational use of PPPs	Promote the availability of PPPs that effectively control pests without harming health or environment	Promote techniques that minimise the risks related to the use of PPPs	Step up monitoring of the marketing of PPPs	Improve controls on the use of PPPs	Reduce the risk arising from the use of PPPs in specific areas	Improve and extend the use of plant protection alerts for citizens and the vulnerable population
Main Quantitative targets	50 annual information campaigns	2 EIP-Agri OGs for IPM and sustainable use of PPPs (end 2024)	IPM guidelines covering at least 92% of UAA (end 2024)	Registration tool for PPPs	Compliance with the requirements for authorisation of all air treatments	Improve the collection of agricultural waste	per year: 4 000 inspections of farms, 500 inspections of PPP treatment companies.	Proposal for measures or recommended practices to promote biodiversity in	At least one protocol of plant protection alerts to the public (referring to the plant health)
	3 annual campaigns or open days		At least three pests shall be monitored in each region	Creation of a unit for the evaluation of low-risk active substances	Inspecting equipment used to apply plant protection products	The proportion of farmers handling their own packaging to exceed 60%	At least one official inspection laboratory per Autonomous Community	At least one training day per year per Autonomous Community	
	750 annual inspections of training bodies		At least 8 IPM demonstration farms		Inspect all application equipment on board aircraft by 2024	The percentage of packaging handled to reach 60% of the packaging placed on the market.	At least 70% of agricultural holdings are using the electronic farm logbook at the end of 2024		
	Website for PPP use and IPM				Inspect all equipment installed inside greenhouses by end 2024	20% of the registered supplier establishments will be checked annually			

Source: Compiled by AUA based on the analysis of the NAPs and completed by interviews with the NCAs

Measuring and Reporting in the risk and use of PPPs

The Commission considers IPM as one of the cornerstones of the SUD, and that its full implementation is necessary in order to reduce dependency on pesticide use. Nevertheless, reducing the use of pesticides is not an explicit objective per se of the SUD, but it was assumed that implementation of IPM and an increased use of alternative methods to control pests would lead to a

⁴³ [Spain - National Action Plan for the sustainable use of plant protection products \(2022\)](#)

use reduction, whether this has happened remains uncertain. While many of the SUD provisions have been implemented in most Member States, and likely contributed to a reduced risk of pesticide use as suggested by the decrease of Harmonised Risk Indicator 1 (HRI 1)⁴⁴ by 20% over the last five-year period (2014-2018), this finding is not consistent across other indicators (i.e., observed decrease in biodiversity in rural ecosystems, MRL exceedance trend and the increase in Harmonised Risk Indicator 2 (HRI 2)⁴⁵), which indicates the limitations of the ability to definitively state whether there has been a reduction of risk (Ramboll et al., 2021).

On 30 August 2023, the Commission published updated EU Harmonised Risk Indicators for pesticides for the period 2011-2021 for the EU. HRI 1, measuring the use and risk of pesticides, shows a decrease of 38% since the baseline period in 2011-2013 and a 6% decline compared to 2020. HRI 2, which is based on the number of emergency authorisations, shows an increase of 41% since the baseline period in 2011-2013 and a 3% decrease compared to 2020. Up to this point, it has not been possible to establish a more sophisticated HRI 2 as only a limited number of Member States have recorded the scale of these authorisations. However, the guidance on emergency authorisations was updated with effect from 1 March 2021, so that Member States are now required to report the area treated in each case. The Commission's proposal for a new Regulation on the Sustainable Use of Plant Protection Products includes a modified HRI 2, which will include this new data to better reflect the risks linked to emergency authorisations. Nevertheless, these results show a moderate progress in risk reduction and support the achievement of the Farm to Fork pesticide reduction targets.

⁴⁴ HRI 1 is based on data on pesticide sales reported to the Commission by Member States under [Regulation \(EC\) No 1185/2009](#).

⁴⁵ HRI 2 is based on the number of emergency authorisations reported to the Commission by Member States using the E-Submission Food Chain (ESFC) Platform, which replaced the [Plant Protection Management System \(PPPAMS\)](#) in January 2023. The indicators are calculated using the methodology laid down in Annex IV of Directive 2009/128/EC.

Graph 1: Harmonised Risk Indicator 1 ([EC, Food Safety, 2023](#))

Graph 2: Harmonised Risk Indicator 2 ([EC, Food Safety, 2023](#))

Poor IPM implementation - Guidelines - Incentives

The assessment of the implementation of IPM by Member States continues to be the most widespread weakness in the application of the SUD. Member States have not converted the IPM general principles into prescriptive and assessable criteria to be applied by users. Therefore, Competent Authorities do not have prescriptive and assessable criteria in order to determine compliance with IPM, and therefore there is limited evidence that IPM is systematically applied (COM(2020)204).

Development and dissemination of IPM practices could be key to effective IPM implementation. The European Commission has recently published a public database presenting an overview of the IPM practices currently available, including the 'crop-specific guidelines' developed by Member States in the implementation of the SUD, accompanied by a study assessing their effectiveness and prospects for their further uptake. This overview of practices was established following a two-year Pilot Project 'IPM Toolbox for farmers' (EC, 2023). This toolbox, with its database containing the available IPM methods and practices, intends to inspire national authorities when developing crop-specific rules adapted to local/regional agro-climatic conditions, and to inspire farm advisors and professional users to implement them. The inventory on crop- and sector-specific guidelines had the objective of identifying and gathering the guidelines in place in the Member States as referred to in Article 14(5) of the SUD Directive. Since there is no specific definition established for the sector- and crop-specific guidelines mentioned in Article 14(5), the nature of the documents developed in the Member States differs considerably and this resulted in some difficulties concerning the identification of relevant documents. Some National Competent Authorities (NCAs) consulted about the guidelines could not provide clear information and others were not sure about what documents were referred to. Answering what crop-specific guidelines regarding IPM exist at Member State level, and what they entail, proved to be a rather complex question with a variety of different answers. The inventory of guidelines includes and describes the documents identified per Member State, as well as related information such as coverage of crops, coverage of IPM principles, target audience of the guidelines, whether they include any obligations for farmers, and whether they are used by authorities for control. The inventory of guidelines was fed into the EU-wide database which enables the consultation of the information related to these guidelines as well as links to the relevant documents when available online.

Table xxx shows the coverage of existing crop-specific guidelines by country and type of crop (Council Decision (EU) 2022/2572 - Commission response). In several Member States, the guidelines cover various crops, generally of main importance to the agricultural sector of the country. However, the total amount of crops/guidelines differs. For example, in Sweden, the guidelines cover 10 different crops, while Latvia's guidelines cover 26 different crops. Croatia and Belgium have elaborated guidelines covering production sectors rather than specific crops, including arable farming, fruit growing, vegetable production, etc.

Table 4: Overview of existing IPM guidelines across SUPPORT countries (no data for Netherlands and Romania)

Country	Crops coverage					
	Arable crops	Viticulture	F&V	Ornamental	Horizontal	Other
BE-Wallonia	X	X	X	X	-	X
BE-Flanders	X	X	X	-	X	X
Germany	X	-	-	-	-	X
Denmark	X	-	-	-	-	-
Spain	X	X	X	-	-	X
France	X	X	X	-	-	X
Greece	X	X	X	-	-	X
Italy	X	X	X	-	-	X
Poland	X	X	X	-	-	X

In Germany, existing guidelines are divided into two parts, where the first one covers overarching areas (preventive measures, natural control mechanisms, decision-making aids, etc.), and a second part provides guidance in relation to specific pests. In the Netherlands, and Romania, no officially approved guidelines were identified. However, this does not mean that cropping IPM guidance is not available in these countries, as in several (if not all) EU Member States a variety of public and private guidelines and guidance, often referred to as cropping guidelines co-exist with the officially approved/official crop-specific guidelines in the context of Article 14(5) of the SUD Directive. In France, four national crop specific guidelines per group of crops have been developed (fruits, vegetables, tropical crops, polyculture farming) and loaded on the ECOPHYTO website. The main specificity of these guidelines is to provide general information and to indicate to the readers that more information must be consulted to be able to understand what to do at farm level. Therefore,

these guidelines are linked to national, regional, and local cropping guidelines developed by public and private organisations (e.g. technical institutes, chambers of agriculture).

The initial idea was to develop additional crop specific guidelines to cover the remaining sectors, but this work has not been completed as the guidelines have not shown any significant added value and were not largely used by farmers. The technical information included in these national documents was perceived as too generic and not adapted to any specific local use. In addition, these guidelines do not include any regulatory obligation.

In most Member States, the guidelines have the aim to provide guidance to farmers, however, in some countries, they are used also for control of IPM implementation by authorities. This is the case in Belgium for example, where different regional guidelines have been developed for Wallonia and Flanders, providing both guidance for the farmers, as well as one part used for verification and control. While Belgium, Italy and Greece have elaborated the guidelines at regional level, the rest of the Member States have developed guidelines at national level. In the case of Italy, a first general guideline has been developed at national level, and then more specific versions at the regional level. For the majority of the crop-specific guidelines, the target audience was the farmers directly, i.e. without the support of technical advisors. Even though it was often suggested that the support from advisors may provide added value. In Poland, there are guidelines in place targeting farmers, as well as other guidelines targeting advisors. Furthermore, in Belgium, there are parts of the guidelines directed to the farmers and other parts used for inspections. Similarly, in Italy, the national general guidelines are not specific enough to be applied by farmers, while the regional guidelines are.

Poland's National Action Plan has successfully implemented integrated pest management principles, reducing risks from plant protection products. Legal provisions and system solutions aligned with Directive 2009/128/EC have been adopted, some of which were pre-existing. Plant protection product use, though increasing, remains lower than in other European countries with intensive agriculture. Food and feed testing reveals minimal exceedances of residue values, indicating food safety. Human poisoning cases from plant protection products have decreased from 616 in 2013 to 450 in 2016. The current National Action Plan builds on lessons from the previous plan, taking into account European Commission mission findings. It modifies some previous actions and introduces new ones to address current needs in reducing PPP-related risks. Integrated pest management principles are a key objective. Widespread implementation of these principles by professional and non-professional users is crucial for rational and sustainable PPP use and pollinating insect protection. The plan includes measurable indicators for assessing risks to human and animal health and the environment. Public participation was ensured through input from research, agricultural organizations, and public administration bodies during the plan's preparation

Apart from guidelines, Belgium, France, Greece, Italy, and the Netherlands employ various incentives to encourage IPM adoption, including financial support and certification systems. These incentives aim to motivate farmers to transition to sustainable pest management practices. Denmark emphasizes IPM through its agriculture policy but focuses on collaborative initiatives between stakeholders. Germany, with its regional variations in incentives, may experience differing levels of IPM adoption. Romania has a framework for incentivizing IPM but may need further development in this regard to encourage broader adoption.

France, Greece, and Italy show considerable emphasis on non-chemical pest control methods. They recognize the value of reducing chemical dependency and have actively promoted alternative pest control techniques. Belgium, Denmark, the Netherlands, and Romania acknowledge non-chemical methods, though they may have slightly less emphasis. Germany follows a regional approach, which can lead to variations in the promotion of non-chemical methods within the country. Germany, Greece, and Romania encounter difficulties in balancing chemical and non-chemical pest control methods. France, Italy, and the Netherlands grapple with varying stakeholder interests and perspectives on IPM. Emphasis on non-chemical pest control methods varies, and enhanced stakeholder integration and cooperation are recommended for all countries. Legal provisions may

need further clarity in some countries to ensure consistent and effective enforcement. Ongoing legal disputes related to IPM are noted in Belgium, Denmark, and France.

Belgium, Denmark, France, Greece, Italy, the Netherlands, and Romania all have training programs for professionals involved in pesticide use and conduct public awareness campaigns. These initiatives aim to educate both agricultural professionals and the general public about the importance of responsible pest management. Germany also has training programs, but their effectiveness may vary regionally.

In conclusion, while these countries share common goals in promoting sustainable pest management through IPM, differences exist in the emphasis placed on non-chemical methods, legal provisions, incentives, and regional approaches. To create a unified EU IPM framework, harmonization efforts should consider these variations and aim for clear, consistent, and effective policies that encourage IPM adoption while protecting the environment and ensuring food safety.

3.3.2. CAP Strategic Plans (CSPs)

The aim of this section is to offer insights into the implementation aspects of the CAP Strategic Plans (CSPs) within the 10 Member States (MS) participating in the SUPPORT project, concerning the promotion of integrated pest management (IPM), and to evaluate the plans' relevance and their role in advancing IPM practices and PPPs reduction.

Developing their CSPs, Member States had to ensure they contribute to the long-term targets set or derive from the legislation on the sustainable use of plant protection products. The Common Agricultural Policy (CAP)—which supports agricultural production in the EU through a system of interventions—is the main funding source the EU has for implementing the Farm to Fork targets and the transition to sustainable agri-food systems.

The CSPs contain a wide range of **mandatory and voluntary measures** addressing pesticide use and increasing the resilience of the cropping systems. In fact the IPM is largely included into the mechanism of conditionality, through the GAEC framework, as crop rotation, biodiversity areas and no-spray zones are important elements of IPM. Some of them contain specific measures to promote IPM, such as eco-schemes, environmental, climate-related and other management commitments, investments, farm advisory services, training activities and knowledge exchange.

The system of **new conditionality** links full receipt of CAP support to the compliance of farmers and other beneficiaries with basic standards concerning the environment, climate change, public health, plant health and animal welfare. The basic standards encompass in a streamlined form a list of statutory management requirements (SMRs) and standards of good agricultural and environmental conditions of land (GAEC standards). The GAEC 7 obligation ensures that crop rotation, allowing for breaking the life cycles of pests and diseases, will take place on around 85% of the arable land supported by the CAP. In most of the CSPs, the standard ensures that every year, a significant share of the arable land at holding level will be subject to a change of crop and almost all plans also include a requirement that a change of main crop must take place at the latest after 3 years. Maintenance of fallow land and landscape features that harbour beneficial organisms (such as insects) which also help combating these pests and diseases is supported through mandatory standard GAEC 8. The CSPs also require (GAEC 4) or compensate farmers for areas where pesticides may not be used, such as on buffer strips along water courses. Another contribution comes from the protection of permanent grasslands (31% of the EU UAA⁴⁶) under GAEC 1 (and environmentally sensitive grasslands under GAEC 9) given that the use of pesticides on these areas is occasional and limited to herbicides against specific weeds (in specific circumstances of unsuitable soil management). The newly introduced statutory management requirement (SMR 8) links to the SUD for certification of users and equipment, management of packaging and remnants and restrictions of pesticide use in sensitive areas, means that infringements found in relation to these requirements may also lead to reduction of CAP payments under the mechanism of conditionality.

Nevertheless, Member States have a certain latitude to define the GAEC standards in their CSPs. This flexibility leads Member States to make different choices, leading to different environmental and climate contributions. For instance, under GAEC 7, crop rotation is mandatory on 40% of the UAA in Poland while it is mandatory on 35% of the UAA in France. As a result, the enhanced conditionality proposed in this new CAP does not provide a common ground of environmental and climate ambition for all countries. Finally, the introduction of GAEC 2 on the protection of wetland and peatland is welcome, but it is observed that in some of the cases studied (e.g. in Poland) the implementation is delayed and the details are not clear. It is therefore not possible to estimate the potential contribution of this GAEC standard at EU-level at this point. (IEEP, April 2023)

⁴⁶ [Quality Climate Change and Air](#)

Thanks to the **voluntary interventions**, such as eco-schemes and environmental, climate-related and other management commitments (AECC), financial support is given to farmers to reduce the reliance on chemical pesticides through e.g., the adoption of enhanced integrated pest management principles, including biological control methods, technologies for precision farming and better application of plant protection products. Eco-schemes provide support for active farmers who apply agricultural practices beneficial for the climate, the environment and animal welfare. They support new or existing practices, in the latter case usually on larger areas compared to 2014-2020. In the green architecture of the CAP, eco-schemes have to go beyond conditionality.

When drafting their CSPs, Member States were required to link the CAP interventions to different results indicators. To quantify the coverage of specific actions which lead to a sustainable and reduced use of pesticides with CAP support, the annual result indicator R.24 *'Sustainable and reduced use of pesticides: Share of utilised agricultural area (UAA) under supported specific commitments which lead to a sustainable use of pesticides in order to reduce risks and impacts of pesticides such as pesticides leakage'* was defined.

Overall, 26.6% of EU agricultural land is planned to be subject to support specifically requiring reduction or more sustainable use of pesticides (beyond requirements of conditionality). The correlation between the R.24 CAP indicator and the objectives outlined in the European Green Deal (EGD) is somewhat fragile. Among the SUPPORT countries, namely Belgium-Wallonia, Germany, Greece, France, and Italy, the Common Strategic Frameworks (CSPs) exhibit a noteworthy commitment to achieving sustainable and reduced pesticide usage. Notably, France has set the indicator at an ambitious 61%, which is the highest among the EU Member States. In contrast, Spain, the Netherlands, Romania and Poland have established less ambitious targets, with percentages of 5%, 7%, 8% and 9,4% respectively.

Figure 3: Share of UAA under supported specific commitments which lead to a sustainable use of pesticides (R.24) - the Support countries in yellow.

Pesticide reduction is listed as among the areas of action at least 2 of which must in principle be included in eco-schemes. **Eco-schemes** are voluntary for farmers (but mandatory for Member States) and they should represent at least 25% of the direct payments. Among the SUPPORT countries, BE-FL, DE, DK, EL, ES, FR, IT, PL and RO allocate funding lower than 25% to eco-schemes,

while BE-WA allocates 26% and NL 32%. Through eco-schemes, 21 out of the 28 CSPs contribute to a reduction in the use of plant protection products. Examples of commitments supported within eco-schemes are implementation of integrated pest management going beyond minimum requirements, application of a ban or limitation in the use of (certain) plant protection products, promoting biological control or use of pheromones, and/or application of mechanical weeding.

	AT	BE-FL	BE-W	BG	CY	CZ	DE	DK	EE	EL	ES	FI	FR	HR	HU	IE	IT	LT	LU	LV	MT	NL	PL	PT	RO	SE	SI	SK	
Integrated production																													
IPM/pesticide management																													
Nutrient management																													
Soil conservation practices																													
Organic farming																													
Landscape and biodiversity																													
Wetlands and peatlands																													
Grassland and grazing																													
Animals and animal welfare																													
Precision farming																													
Water management																													

Figure 4: CSPs according to thematic coverage of eco-schemes (EC, 2023).

Environmental measures for the sustainable and reduced use of pesticides are covered via eco-schemes by all the SUPPORT countries except Spain and Romania that do not address this thematic area with eco-schemes (**Table 5**).

Table 5: CSPs according to Eco-schemes and R.24

Member State	National Intervention Code	Intervention Name - English	Total EU expenditure (2023-2029)	Max Annual Planned Output (2023-2027)
Belgium-Flanders				
	1.6	Ecologically managed grassland	24.490.620	17,402 ha
	1.8	Cultivation of environmentally, biodiversity-friendly and/or climate-resilient crops (abbreviated: Ecocropping)	20.186.280	7,334 ha
	1.9	Continuation of organic farming (abbreviated: Continuation bio)	5.982.600	12,925 ha
	1.10	Buffer strips	35.086.350	7,378 ha
	1.11	Mechanical weed control	8.308.620	6,102 ha
	1.14	Precision agriculture 1.0	4.001.400	29,380 ha
Belgium-Wallonia				
	142	Eco-schemes - environmentally-friendly crops	30.547.440	17,661 ha
	144 - Eco-régimes	Reduction of inputs	30.680.000	76,700 ha
Germany				
	DZ-0401	Provision of land to improve biodiversity and conservation of habitats	1.604.913.092	703,173 ha
	DZ-0406	Management of arable or permanent cropland on the holding without the use of chemically synthesised plant protection products	692.472.018	1,508,278 ha
Denmark				
	5	Eco scheme for organic area aid	254.220.267	617,349 ha
	9	Eco scheme for biodiversity and sustainability	91.947.500	50,000 ha
Greece				

	Π1-31.2	Extension of the application of ecological focus areas	21.403.729	244,574 ha
	Π1-31.3	Implementation of improved green cover practices, while enhancing biodiversity	179.455.112	323,167 ha
	Π1-31.4	Circular economy applications in agriculture	94.690.040	144,860 ha
	Π1-31.6	Aid for producers for the implementation of environmentally-friendly management practices, using a digital application for management of inputs and monitoring of environmental parameters	252.252.876	210,655 ha
	Π1-31.8	Maintenance and protection of crops on terraced land	22.500.000	45,000 ha
	Π1-31.9	Conservation of organic farming and livestock farming.	1.199.084.365	845,629 ha
France				
	31.01	Eco-scheme	8.557.690.171	21,490,188 ha
Italy				
	PD 04 - ES 5	ECO - diagram 5 SPECIFIC MEASURES FOR IMPOLLINATOR	218.363.330	93,109 ha
	PD 05 - ES 2	ECO - diagram 2 Inherption of tree crops	782.238.061	1,250,742 ha
	PD 05 - ES 4	ECO - Figure 4 Extensive fodder systems with rotation	819.190.065	1,397,612 ha
Netherlands				
	I.31	Eco-scheme for climate and living environment	963.897.707	1,523,093 ha
Poland				
	I 4.1	Eco-scheme - Areas with melliferous plants	39.488.700	30,000 ha
	I 4.3	Eco-scheme - Plant production under the Integrated Plant Production scheme	40.522.078	29,800 ha

	14.4	Eco-scheme - Organic crop protection	2.197.550	5,000 ha
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Belgium, Germany, Greece and Poland have introduced eco-schemes that clearly promote IPM practices.

In its CSP, **Belgium Flanders** describes that precision agriculture stands as a crucial catalyst for technological innovation, employing precise data to elevate a farm's environmental and climate performance. "**Precision agriculture 1.0**" employs GPS-controlled machines equipped with real-time kinematic (RTK) capabilities for the targeted application of fertilizers and crop protection products. The automation of these processes guarantees accurate and efficient fertilization, reducing overlap and preventing double application. This intervention not only fosters sustainability in farming operations but also augments the farm's comprehensive environmental and climate performance.

In **Belgium-Wallonia**, the eco-scheme "**Reduction of inputs**" involves an eco-regime where farmers are financially rewarded for abstaining from the application of specific plant protection products on their arable land and permanent crops.

Germany's eco-scheme on the management of arable or permanent crop areas of the holding without the use of chemical-synthetic plant protection products incentivise conventional farms to minimize or reduce the use of chemical pesticides with great benefits for water quality. The eco-scheme offers a low remuneration which carries the risk of low uptake by farmers. At the same time, it is not clear if the eco-scheme can be applied by organic farms and how to avoid double payment through organic farming support measures.

Greece's eco-scheme "**Aid for producers for the implementation of environmentally-friendly management practices, using a digital application for management of inputs and monitoring of environmental parameters**", aims to assist producers in acquiring and employing digital applications for inputs management and environmental data monitoring. Additionally, producers, under the guidance of an advisor, implement selected practices from a recommended list. Encouraged for purchase, the digital application license includes comprehensive information such as the agricultural holding's data, soil sampling results, and details on management practices, crop history, and performance objectives. This encompasses various aspects of cultivation operations, including nutrient and plant protection product applications, irrigation, compliance with legal requirements, nutrient balances, active plant protection substances, water consumption, and estimates of carbon footprint. Producers have the option to choose from approved applications that meet specific criteria, including automatic data integration, two-way communication with authorities, adherence to EU principles, and ensuring data security and privacy.

Poland's eco-scheme '**Conducting plant production under the Integrated Plant Production scheme**' supports integrated plant production methods, thus promoting various practices having a positive impact on water quality: integrated pest management, use of non-chemical PPPs, fertilisation adapted to the nutritional needs of plants, using up-to-date soil tests on nutrients and soil pH, obligation to maintain permanent grassland, which improves water retention in soils, obligation to comply with integrated pest management principles. Chemical protection is still allowed when it is not possible to eliminate pathogens through other methods. Nevertheless the insufficient budget of €40.5m and the small targeted area (between 24,500 and 29,800 ha annually), are limiting the potential benefits for water protection (IEEP, 2023).

Eco-schemes can be programmed next to **AECM** or operate as an intermediate instrument between conditionality and AECM, that should cover additional costs and income foregone only resulting from commitments going beyond the baseline of mandatory standards and requirements established in

Union and national law. AECM include payments for environmental, climate-related and other management commitments that Member States should support throughout their territories, in accordance with their specific national, regional or local needs. Member States should grant payments to farmers and other land managers who undertake, on a voluntary basis, management commitments that contribute to climate change mitigation and adaptation and to the protection and improvement of the environment. Support for management commitments may in particular include payments for types of intervention supporting environmentally friendly production systems such as agro-ecology, conservation agriculture and integrated production.

The AECMs show a huge variety, reflecting the different needs that exist in the Member States. With more than 200 AECM interventions for the whole EU, the number of AECMs per Member States ranges from two (NL) to more than 40 (IT). Agri-environment-climate commitments contained in CSPs will also be used to support precision application technologies and early monitoring of pests and to reward land managers for applying IPM principles, such as by abiding with crop specific IPM rules, use of traditional or tolerant crop varieties that need less pesticides, or switching to extensive crop rotations, incorporating biodiversity friendly crops and/or soil enrichment crops within rotations or using natural enemies/biological control which reduce the likelihood of pest infestations and thereby need for pesticides, and mechanical weeding. Through agri-environment-climate commitments, 22 CSPs (including BE-Flanders, Greece, Spain, France, Italy, Netherlands, Poland and Romania) schedule support for sustainable plant protection actions while six CSPs (including Germany, Spain and Italy) for application of precision farming with one specifically supporting low input systems (EC, 2023).

	AT	BE-FL	BE-WA	BG	CY	CZ	DE	DK	EE	EL	ES	FI	FR	HR	HU	IE	IT	LT	LU	LV	MT	NL	PL	PT	RO	SE	SI	SK
Plant Protection																												
Fertilisation and Soil Amendment																												
Manure Storage																												
Soil Management																												
Crop Rotation Diversification																												
Landscape																												
Forestry																												
Grasslands and Grazing																												
Animals																												
Other Species																												
Water management																												
Bioeconomy Energy Efficiency																												
Management Plans																												
Precision Farming																												
Certification Schemes																												
Organic Farming																												
Low Input Systems																												
Training																												

Figure 5: CSPs according to thematic coverage of agri-environment climate commitments (EC, 2023)

Environmental measures for the sustainable and reduced use of pesticides are covered via AECM by all the SUPPORT countries except Denmark that do not address this thematic area with AECM (Table 6).

Table 6: CSPs according to AECMs and R.24

Member State	National Intervention Code	Intervention Name	Total EU expenditure (2023-2029)	Total Public Expenditure (2023-2029)	Max of Annual Planned Output (2023-

					2029) Ha
Belgium-Flanders					
	3.5	Perennial flower strip in fruit production (abbreviated: Multiannual flower strip of fruit)	525.030	1.221.000	520
	3.8	Management agreements for the buffering of vulnerable nature or sensitive natural elements or for the creation of ecological links (abbreviated: Buffering and linking management agreements)	8.332.648	19.378.250	3.450
	3.10	Management agreements for the protection of fauna and flora linked to agricultural activities (abbreviated: Management agreements for species protection)	25.206.665	47.923.892	10.260
Belgium-Wallonia					
	312	MAEC — Parks developed	9.041.587	24.384.000	4.900
	315	MAEC — Herbage supplies	6.408.610	17.283.200	5.000
Germany					
	EL-0101	Management commitments to improve climate change mitigation	114.278.016	148.706.312	171.798
	EL-0102	Management commitments to improve water quality	153.527.272	222.335.721	453.018
	EL-0105	Management commitments to improve biodiversity	1.320.634.653	1.689.522.464	1.870.782
Greece					
	Π3-70-1.2	Aid for the protection of the rural landscape	8.795.320	10.551.150	2.924
	Π3-70-1.3	Application of alternative plant protection methods to reduce pesticides	239.205.157	281.759.402	134.208
Spain					
	6501.1	Agri-environment commitments on agricultural areas (6501.1 IACS). Integrated production.	65.590.971	87.103.816	68.910

	6501.2	Agri-environment commitments on agricultural areas (6501.2 IACS). Commitments on sustainable crops.	134.567.703	190.660.319	286.495
	6501.7	Agri-environment commitments on agricultural areas (6501.7 IACS). Alternative to chemical control.	15.358.198	33.837.505	87.330
France					
	70.06	Agri-environment-climate measure for water quality and quantitative management for hexagon arable crops	186.316.880	232.896.100	354.126
Italy					
	SRA01	ACA 1 – Integrated production	233.264.480	518.543.430	424.997
	SRA05	ACA5 – grass cover tree crops	13.623.113	28.656.296	11.638
	SRA06	ACA6 – cover crops	15.058.915	36.845.000	30.867
	SRA07	ACA7 – conversion of arable land to grassland	8.109.313	17.766.274	38.130
	SRA08	ACA8 – management of permanent grassland and pasture	85.802.716	207.159.008	301.466
	SRA10	ACA10 – Active management of ecological infrastructure	22.134.997	54.385.741	75.608
	SRA12	ACA12 – crops losing ecological corridors	782.300	1.900.000	1.110
	SRA19	ACA19 – reduction in plant protection products	11.559.500	28.300.000	25.474
	SRA24	ACA24 – Precision farming practices	16.285.349	33.949.259	38.404
	SRA25	ACA25 – protection of tree crops of environmental and landscape value	14.707.575	31.862.593	7.900
	SRA26	ACA26 – set-aside	10.989.000	27.000.000	5.877
	TRABR-10.1.2	Transition – Improvement of pastures and meadows – Abruzzo grazing	1.827.500	4.300.000	37.000
	TRLOM-10.1.01	Transition – Lombardy Integrated Agricultural Production	7.733.000	19.000.000	15.000
	TRLOM-10.1.02	Transition – rotation with fodder legumes Lombardy	20.350	50.000	300
Netherlands					

	I.70.1	Agricultural Nature and Landscape Management (ANLb)	364.000.000	560.000.000	129.975
Poland					
	I 8.1.	Conservation of valuable habitats and endangered species in Natura 2000 sites	189.977.108	237.471.385	264.432
	I 8.2.	Conservation of valuable habitats and endangered species outside Natura 2000 sites	241.106.053	301.382.566	350.068
	I 8.3.	Extensive use of meadows and pastures in Natura 2000 sites	14.139.096	17.673.870	31.358
	I 8.4.	Conservation of orchards of traditional varieties of fruit trees	561.362	701.702	492
	I 8.7.	Biodiversity on arable land	2.232.150	2.790.188	1.416
	I.8.9.1.	AGRI-environment-climate commitments implemented under the agri-environment-climate measure of the RDP 2014-2020. Package 4. Current habitats and endangered bird species in Natura 2000 sites	14.679.759	18.349.699	55.204
	I.8.9.2.	AGRI-environment-climate commitments implemented under the Agri-environment-climate measure of the Rural Development Programme 2014-2020 (RDP 2014-2020). Package 5. Valuable habitats outside Natura 2000 sites	13.388.676	16.735.845	47.787
Romania					
	DR-01	Agri-environment and climate on permanent grassland	328.326.264	386.266.193	610.590
	DR-02	Agri-environment and climate on arable land	88.986.750	104.690.294	202.200

France, Greece, Italy and Spain have introduced AECMs that clearly promote IPM practices.

Biological control methods are key innovations as part of the Integrated Pest Management. They are essential to move away from chemical pesticides and to help reach the Farm to Fork reduction targets. **Greece** plans an agri-environment-climate intervention "**Application of alternative plant protection methods to reduce pesticides**" providing for application of these alternative methods of plant protection, which includes the pheromone-based Comfuzio method, whereby insects are prevented from mating. The intervention aims to encourage the adoption of alternative plant protection methods, reducing reliance on chemical PPPs by providing support to farmers. It consists of two actions. Action 1 focuses on alternative weed control in rice fields to avoid chemical PPPs, while Action 2, named "CONFUSIO," aims to prevent the mating of insect pests in selected crops. Action 2 complements another initiative promoting environmentally friendly practices. The

implementation involves a digital input management system, emphasizing the continuation of the Confusio method, particularly in newly included crop areas.

France has incorporated measures that target specific aspects of water quality or quantity. This is the case, for instance, with one of the sub-measures in the flat-rate payment for the transition of practices. Under this sub-measure, farmers receive a payment if they reduce their pesticide Treatment Frequency Index⁴⁷ by 30% over 5 years. While this result-based payment could have benefits in participating farms, it is likely that very few farms will take part as the budget is likely to be very small (an unknown portion of the 135 million euros dedicated for this intervention). The overall effect of such sub-measure is thus likely to be small. Moreover, the target set in the payment (-30% in the Treatment Frequency Index) is substantially lower than the targets defined in the European Farm to Fork Strategy (-50% of pesticide use by 2030) and in France's National Ecophyto II Plan (-50% of pesticide use in 2025 compared to 2015) (IEEP, 2023).

Italy designed several AECM interventions that promote IPM. The **ACA10 – 'Active Management of Ecological Infrastructure'**, bans the chemical control of pests and the application of fertilisers along water courses and introduces mowing obligations and grazing restrictions, preserving landscape elements and water quality.

The **ACA 1-"Integrated Production"** intervention supports beneficiaries committed to adhering to technical provisions outlined in the IPM guidelines. Compliance involves following the National Integrated Production Quality System, with approved regional variations. This commitment aligns with voluntary IPM applications under the SUD. The intervention enhances producer awareness, ensures efficient fulfillment of obligations, and reduces errors through compliance checks. Although demanding more from producers, this approach provides timely feedback on measure execution and justifies public spending support. The intervention adheres to national legislation, particularly in relation to tobacco production under Directive 2014/40/EU. Technical provisions introduce agronomic and crop protection practices, improving soil management, fertilization, water use for irrigation, and phytosanitary protection. Guidelines include practices like crop rotation and grassing of inter-rows for trees to mitigate soil erosion, enhance organic substance supply, and reduce carbon dioxide emissions. Crop fertilization provisions establish maximum nutrient quantities based on soil analysis, contributing to rationalized and reduced fertilizer inputs to minimize pollution potential. Irrigation provisions involve recording rainfall and irrigation data for efficient water resource monitoring. Phytosanitary defense and weed control provisions outline plant monitoring methods. Overall, the intervention emphasizes sustainable agricultural practices, biodiversity preservation, and climate change resilience.

The **ACA 10 - Active management of ecological infrastructure** intervention involves an annual payment to beneficiaries who voluntarily commit to managing ecological infrastructures. These infrastructures are categorized into various actions, each targeting specific ecological components such as tree/shrub formations, linear herbaceous formations, groves, wet meadows, marcite, minor hydraulic networks, agricultural terraced areas, basins, and natural water sources.

The **ACA19 – "Reduction of the Impact of the Use of Plant Protection Products"** intervention provides per-hectare support to beneficiaries adopting agronomic management techniques. These techniques aim to minimize the use of plant protection products, reducing the use of active substances identified for replacement under EU regulations and implementing advanced protection methods beyond mere limitation in product use. The intervention aligns with the broader goal of

⁴⁷ The Phytosanitary Treatment Frequency Index (TFI) is an indicator for monitoring the use of plant protection products on a farm or group of farms. The TFI counts the number of reference doses used per hectare during a crop year.

sustainable agricultural management, aiming to mitigate environmental pressures from the primary sector and gradually contain their impact on environmental resources. Specifically, it complements the objectives of the Farm to Fork strategy, the Italian National Action Plan (NAP) and the Water Framework Directive. The intervention also supports the "Biodiversity Strategy" by promoting reduced pesticide use and the adoption of advanced crop protection systems. The intervention is structured into three actions:

Action 1: Aims to reduce the use of plant protection products by 50% through the adoption of specific techniques and equipment.

Action 2: Targets a reduction in the use of pesticides containing environmentally harmful active substances, aligning with EU regulations.

Action 3: Encourages the adoption of advanced crop protection strategies based on biotechnological and organic methods.

The **ACA24 – "Reduction of Chemical and Water Inputs through the Adoption of Agricultural Practices Precision"** intervention offers annual support per hectare to beneficiaries adopting precision agriculture practices. The primary goal is to quantitatively reduce chemical and water inputs in agricultural production by employing precision agriculture practices, enabling a sustainable production system with variable input application precision (regarding timing, quantity, and location). This approach aligns with the "National Guidelines for the development of Precision Agriculture in Italy," emphasizing environmental protection and climate action. The intervention aims to enhance resource efficiency, decrease pollution and degradation risks associated with plant protection products and fertilizers, promote rational water use for irrigation, and positively impact sustainable soil management. Additionally, it addresses the challenge of obtaining agricultural inputs amidst international price increases. Environmental objectives of the intervention align with the Farm to Fork strategy, focusing on a 50% reduction in overall chemical pesticide use and nutrient losses. It also complements the Italian National Action Plan and synergises with the Water Framework Directive and Nitrates Directive. The intervention leverages satellite, meteorological, drone, and sensor data to mitigate environmental pollution and encourage efficient water use by integrating precise agricultural data. This data-driven approach tackles the challenges posed by digitalisation in agriculture, facilitating informed decision-making and targeted technology investments. Through three concurrent measures—precision fertilization, phytosanitary treatments, and irrigation—the intervention enables regions to determine the actions suitable for their territories. While the majority of regions activate all three measures, Umbria opts for activating actions 1 and 2.

Spain plans a set of interventions on helping farmers shift, or maintain, low input intensity systems. These interventions are all planned under AECMs and are integrated production (6501.1), sustainable cultivation commitments (6501.2) and alternatives to chemical control (6501.7). Integrated production⁴⁸ encourages biological control (although it does not prohibit pesticide use) and establishes certain bans which are actually conditionality requirements under the CAP (i.e., burning residues) therefore not providing additional benefits. Given the lack of targets and the low planned output (0.3% of UAA) it is expected to have little impact. It has also only been programmed by a small number of regions, as others have opted to have larger budgets for organic agriculture. Next are the sustainable cultivation commitments (6501.2), which aim to implement "sustainable agriculture". The type of measures supported vary widely among the regions. As in the case of integrated production, the planned output is very small (0.35% of the UAA). Environmental and climate commitment on alternatives to chemical control (6501.7) promotes the use of alternative systems to chemical pest, disease and weed control. However, the application of pesticides is still

⁴⁸ [*Royal Decree 1201/2002, of November 20, which regulates the integrated production of agricultural products.*](#)

allowed in some regions if pests are not under control, some regions target only a limited range of crops and a small percentage of UAA is covered (IEEP, 2023).

The intervention 6501.1 to promote integrated production is programmed in the Canary Islands, Extremadura, Country Basque and Balearic Islands. Catalonia and Andalusia use integrated production as the baseline of their agro-environmental interventions. Castilla-La Mancha, Murcia and the Valencian Community have opted to allocate very high percentages of EAFRD to organic farming intervention, instead of distributing efforts between IPM and organic agriculture. The rest of the Autonomous Communities program interventions that respond to the needs of integrated production. This diversified regional strategy reflects varying priorities and approaches to sustainable agricultural practices across Spain.

The intervention 6501.7 has remained consistent in terms of the number of regions involved, with 4 Autonomous Communities programming it both in 14-20 and 23-27. The lack of expansion is attributed to certain regions choosing organic farming as an alternative method, sometimes viewed as a cost for aid calculation. Notable allocations come from Murcia, Castilla-La Mancha, Balearic Islands, Valencian Community, and Andalusia. The intervention addresses specific needs, but some broader interventions, such as 6501.5 Protection of birdlife, 6501.6 Maintenance or improvement of habitats, and 6501.4 Beekeeping for biodiversity, also contribute to fulfilling these objectives on a larger territorial scale.

The new CSPs also continue to support productive and non-productive, on-farm and off-farm **investments** (Article 73-74). This may concern investments related to the development, modernisation or adaptation of agriculture and forestry including e.g., the sustainable use of water and inputs (such as fertilisers and plant protection products), sustainable forest management, agro-forestry practices and irrigation practices as well as investments in basic services and for the protection of public goods in rural areas. Investments for a sustainable use of PPPs should be captured in R.9 'Farm modernisation: Share of farms receiving investment support to restructure and modernise, including to improve resource efficiency' and/or R.26 'Investments related to natural resources: Share of farms benefitting from CAP productive and non-productive investment support related to care for the natural resources. Funding opportunities for the adoption of technical innovations, such as precision farming technologies that can help farmers improve the sustainability of their farming systems, for instance through reductions in chemical inputs, are included in the CSPs (Table xxx). This is done through various investment interventions, but since they are not directly linked to environmental and climate objectives in the CSP it is not discussed in further detail. In addition, the interventions do not always require farmers to prove that they have reached a particular improvement in relation to a baseline. Investment interventions are designed so that one intervention could support many different types of investments without necessarily specifying them, and the actual supported investments and their contribution to environmental goals such as reducing the use and risk of pesticides will not be known until Member States report on the implementation.

Table 7: CSPs according to rural development investments and R.9/R.26

Member State	National Intervention Code	Intervention Name - English	Total EU expenditure (2023-2029)	Max Annual Planned Output (2023-2027)
Belgium-Flanders				
	3.20	VLIF Innovative investments for further sustainability on farms	97	26
	3.21	VLIF Innovative green investments on farms	117	31

	3.22	VLIF Productive investments for further sustainability on farms	8.372	1.825
	3.23	VLIF Productive green investments on agricultural holdings	8.699	1.936
	3.26	VLIF — Non-productive investments for environmental and climate objectives	2.766	540
	3.30	VLIF – Investments with limited contribution to profitability and targeting environmental and climate objectives	1.544	301
Belgium-Wallonia				
	351	Aid for productive investments in agricultural holdings.	4.274	1.070
	352	Aid for non-productive investments in agricultural holdings	225	53
Germany				
	EL-0403	Individual productive investments in agricultural enterprises	8.732	1.724
Denmark				
	22	Environmental and climate friendly technology	467	167
Greece				
	Π3-73-2.5	Investments on farms to protect against natural disasters, adverse climatic events and catastrophic events	988	582
Spain				
	6841.1	Aid for productive investments on agricultural holdings linked to contributing to climate change mitigation — adaptation, efficient use of natural resources and animal welfare	5753	1311
	6844	Aid for non-productive investments on agricultural holdings linked to climate change mitigation — adaptation, efficient use of natural resources and biodiversity	3608	1110

France				
	73.01	Productive investments on farm: support for primary agricultural production and projects carried out by farmers or their groups	60.458	12.824
	73.02	Non-productive agricultural investments	1.555	379
	73.09	Productive investments on farm — Corsica: support for primary agricultural production and projects carried out by farmers or their groups	1.073	300
	73.10	Non-productive agricultural investments — Corsica	23	6
	73.17	Subsidised investments for young farmers	1.132	273
Italy				
	SRD 18	FINANCIAL INSTRUMENTS: REVOLVING FUNDS FOR PRODUCTIVE AGRICULTURAL INVESTMENTS FOR THE COMPETITIVENESS OF AGRICULTURAL HOLDINGS AND FOR THE ENVIRONMENT, CLIMATE AND ANIMAL WELFARE	78	33
	SRD02	productive agricultural investments for environment, climate and animal welfare	4.974	1.336
	SRD04	non-productive agricultural investments for environmental purposes	3.938	1.018
Netherlands				
	I.73.1b	Productive investment Green — Blue and animal welfare	1.688	448
	I.73.2	Non-productive investments on agricultural holdings	577	125
Romania				
	DR-14	Investments in small farms	2.400	2.400
	DR-19	Non-productive investments at farm level	62	31

Finally, support is still given under rural development to **knowledge transfer** (Article 78), **advisory services** (Art 15) and **cooperation** (Article 77) contributing to the sustainable management and overall performance of agricultural holdings and rural businesses. It should help farmers and other beneficiaries become more aware of the standards, requirements and information on the sustainable use of pesticides, IPM implementation and on nutrient management.

Previous and current CAP legislation requires Member States to establish a system for advising beneficiaries on land management and farm management, and in particular the requirement referred to in Article 14 of SUD on IPM. Under the system beneficiaries and farmers can access advice on good farming practices on a voluntary basis, including IPM (EC, 2020). The CAP foresees technical support to farmers through knowledge exchange, cooperation and advice (Farm Advisory Services). **Advice** to farmers is stepped up through the CSPs, specifically in relation to reducing use of pesticides through e.g. integrated pest management or precision agriculture. More broadly, Member States must provide advice to farmers through the so-called Farm Advisory Services (FAS). The FAS must be linked to research and innovation networks in the Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation System (AKIS). The CAP can finance knowledge transfer, such as setting-up FAS and the use of FAS by farmers.

The Netherlands has planned the intervention '1.77.4 Collaboration for Integrated area development', under the **Cooperation** (Article 77), for integrated area development aimed at achieving specific goals related to climate, water, and biodiversity in agricultural areas. The approach involves engaging farmers and land managers in a collaborative process to analyze their region, create an action plan, and implement it. The intervention consists of two parts: support for preparing an integrated area plan and support for implementing the plan over multiple years. Activities include forming partnerships, formulating area tasks, organizing knowledge-sharing meetings, implementing land consolidation, making investments, testing innovations, and ensuring proper management, administration, and accountability. The intervention aligns with several CAP goals, such as reducing greenhouse gas emissions, improving water and soil quality, and enhancing biodiversity.

Other interventions can potentially contribute to foster sustainable development and efficient management of natural resources such as water, soil and air, including by reducing chemical dependency, such as sectoral interventions (market measures) which can address the difficulties encountered in certain types of production and sectors by improving, amongst other things, the sustainability of the sector. **Market measures**, in particular in the fruits and vegetable sector, may also finance collective approaches for the promotion of environmental practices, including integrated pest management. The CAP Regulation provides that national Operational Programmes must devote part of the budget to environmental practices such as IPM or pesticides reductions. In addition, farmers will also be encouraged, as part of the Rural Development interventions, to invest in new technologies that can allow the implementation of some of the pesticide reduction practices. Be-Wallonia, Germany, Italy and Netherlands plan to support investments mainly in the fruit and vegetables sector (Table xxx).

Table 8: CSPs according to sectoral investments and R24

Member State	National Intervention Code	Intervention Name - English	Sector	Total EU expenditure (2023-2029)	Max Annual Planned Output (2023-2027)
BE-Wallonia					
	2105	Sectoral intervention F – L – Bio or integrated	Fruit and Vegetables	-	-
Germany					
	SP-0106	Organic or integrated production	Fruit and Vegetables	-	-
Italy					
	IS Olivicolo - 47.1d	Operational programmes of Olive Oil and Olive Producer Organisations (POs) and their Associations (APOs)	Olive oil and tables olive	-	-
	ISO Is Ortofrutta04	Operational programmes in the fruit and vegetables sector – Organic or integrated production	Fruit and Vegetables	-	-
	ISP IS patate 04	Operational programmes in the potato sector – Organic or integrated production	Other sectors covering products listed in Annex VI	-	-
Netherlands					
	I.47 - 1(d)	Sectoral Intervention Fruit & Vegetables (SIG&F) - ORGAN(47(1)(d))	Fruit and Vegetables	-	-

4. Research and Innovation

The Commission is supporting a range of research projects to broaden the range of alternative pest control strategies, tools and technologies and to determine the impacts of pesticide use on the environment and human health. The EU Research and Innovation framework programmes, Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe, help to develop a wide range of tools for the prevention, early detection, monitoring, control and management of plant pests and diseases, along with promoting breeding of plant varieties with improved characteristics like pest resistance.

The Commission, through the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation Horizon 2020, supports research and innovation to develop more sustainable pest control strategies, tools and technologies to support IPM, such as new low-risk products, biological controls, decision support tools and to determine the impacts of pesticide use on the environment and human health⁴⁹.

Under Societal Challenge 2, the Commission has provided EUR 159 million⁵⁰ to support research on IPM, emerging risks to plant health, alternatives to chemical pesticides and decision support systems. Moreover, under this work programme, in 2020, it is envisaged to fund a coordination and support action of a European-wide network of IPM demonstration farms, with EUR 6 million earmarked⁵¹. Beyond IPM and plant health, the Commission also supports research on ecological approaches and organic farming to foster the resilience of agriculture⁵².

Furthermore, the European Innovation Partnership 'Agricultural Productivity and Sustainability'⁵³ (EIP-AGRI) connects European research and innovation projects financed under Horizon 2020 with smaller operational groups⁵⁴ working at national and regional level under the rural development policy. The interactive innovation approach promoted by the EIP-AGRI, based on the so-called multi-actor approach, encourages cooperation between actors with different but complementary types of knowledge (researchers, farmers, advisers, businesses, NGOs and others), thus helping bridge the gap between research and practice and foster the uptake of innovations in practice, notably in plant protection and integrated pest management.

Knowledge and innovative solutions are made available to advisors and farmers through Thematic and Advisory Networks funded by EU R&I programmes. In addition, under Horizon Europe, a co-

⁴⁹ Available at: Societal Challenge 2 Work programme 2016-2017 https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/wp/2016_2017/main/h2020-wp1617-food_en.pdf and societal challenge 2 work programme 2018-2020 (SFS-04, SFS-05 and SFS-6) https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/wp/2018-2020/main/h2020-wp1820-food_en.pdf

⁵⁰ Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/food-farming-fisheries/farming/documents/factsheet-agri-plant-health_en.pdf

⁵¹ Available at: SFS-6-2018-2020 in https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/wp/2018-2020/main/h2020-wp1820-food_en.pdf

⁵² Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/information_society/newsroom/image/document/2018-18/agri_factsheets_07_ecological-approaches_ok_1545C778-C5D7-AA24-163D1DD06A4CDF2F_51894.pdf

⁵³ Available at: <https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en>

⁵⁴ Available at: <https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/about/operational-groups>

funded R&I partnership on agroecology is expected to be tentatively launched in 2024. One of its aims will be to maximise the potential of agro-ecology to reduce and phase out the use of pesticides in agriculture, and to maximise the contribution of farming to biodiversity protection and nature restoration. The total tentative budget would be EUR 300 million. Lastly, the EU CAP Network also supports farmers in the transition towards the sustainable use of pesticides. In April 2023 a workshop 'Innovative arable crop protection - using pesticides sustainably' was organised in Amsterdam. It focused on exchanging knowledge and sharing innovative, inspirational practices that support farmers, advisors and other stakeholders to ensure greater uptake of non-chemical plant protection methods in arable crops by using economically and ecologically sustainable approaches.

Dissemination and networking of sustainable practices is of utmost importance to help farmers, advisors and other stakeholders in the transition towards a greater uptake of nonchemical plant protection methods. Many European initiatives, such as IPMWorks (H2020, No. 101000339), IPMDecisions (H2020 No. 817617), SmartProtect (H2020 No. 862563) and Innoseta (H2020 no. 773864) are promoting the adoption of IPM strategies and available tools across Europe to achieve more sustainable farming and plant protection. These fixed term projects develop resources to support advance implementation of IPM towards 'Holistic IPM'. The Horizon 2020 project IPM Works has set an EU-wide network of farmers to demonstrate and promote the benefits of IPM practices.

Priority is given to research measures supporting the Green Deal objectives. Specifically, the EU has supported R&I and knowledge exchange in the area of plant health and plant protection through various instruments and these are summarised as follows: 1. Horizon 2020¹⁴⁴ and Horizon Europe¹⁴⁵: The EU R&I funding framework programmes, Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe, support measures to develop a wide range of tools for prevention, early detection, monitoring, control and management of plant pests and diseases, along with promoting breeding of plant varieties with improved characteristics like pest resistance, and crop management strategies. It also financed a project focused on organic farming: RELACS (replacements of contentious inputs in organic farming systems) and Organic-PLUS, which have achieved important results in relation to reducing and phasing-out the use of some of the most contentious pesticides still used in organic farming.

Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe has financed 37 projects with + EUR 189 million to protect plant health and promote IPM, including by promoting sustainable farming practices such as agro-ecology and organic farming. Over EUR 60 million were dedicated to plant health and plant protection in the first two years of Horizon Europe to finance 10 projects. Several projects implement the 'multiactor approach' to develop demand-driven solutions which are more ready to be applied in practice, accelerating the transition and reaching end-users. Innovative solutions and practical knowledge are also made available to advisors and farmers through Thematic Networks funded by EU R&I programmes.

Moreover, a future Horizon Europe partnership on agroecology is expected to catalyse efforts that will underpin the agroecology transition in Europe. The partnership would constitute a key instrument to foster the implementation of agroecological practices for plant health and to reduce the use of chemical pesticides.

Moreover, through EIP-AGRI strand of the EU CAP Network (previously EIP-AGRI Network), the Commission provides support and promotes, through the organisation of workshop, seminars and focus groups, the exchange and dissemination of best practices among Member States and other stakeholders. Several EIP-AGRI networking activities were organised over the past years helping farmers to produce with a reduced use of chemical pesticides. EIP-AGRI Operational Groups are project-based and support the development of innovations seeking solutions to a certain (practical) problem by groups of relevant actors in a bottom-up manner. From over 2,788 Operational Groups, 475 are working on finding solutions for the sustainable use of pesticides. Examples of EIP-AGRI Operational Groups are accessible on the EU CAP Network website and found at the following links:

- a vineyard app for plant protection; the project ('APPVID') ran between 2016 and 2018 in Spain, bringing together different types of organisations as partners, representing research

and practice. In the first phase of the project, meteorological stations were installed on 9 experimental vineyard plots. In the second phase, disease data for mildew, powdery mildew and botrytis diseases were collected. In parallel, the different components for the mobile application were developed. Finally, the mobile application was developed and made available.

- weed control with non-chemical alternatives; this Operational Group ('HortInf'), is trying to find non-chemical alternatives to conventional weed management that could be used by Portuguese farmers. It is one of 23 Operational Groups working on weed management.
- certification of pesticide residue free fruit & vegetables: 'AGroTrend', the Polish operational Group is developing a zero-residue certification system providing more detailed information to the consumer about the quality of the product they are buying while encouraging further uptake of farming techniques to protect the environment.
- alternatives for stone fruit, berries and table grapes: this Spanish Operational Group 'FruitCare' was created in 2020 and is aimed at establishing pesticide substitution programmes for fruit producers. The study considered the socio-economic impact of the strategies, allowing them to determine the real consequences of the suppression of active substances, as well as the suitability of the alternative strategies proposed, in each crop.

Specific financial support for new technologies and precision farming tools is also part of the Digital Europe Programme which is a new EU funding programme focused on bringing digital technology to businesses, citizens and public administrations. The Digital Europe Programme is implemented by means of multiannual work programmes in 2023-2024, with a total budget of EUR 909,5 million. Measures under the Work programme 2023-2024 will boost the number of education and training opportunities for 'users of advanced digital technologies', such as farm advisors exploiting the potential of precision farming technologies or software experts with specific automotive expertise.

5. Interview-Based Policy Assessment

5.1 EU Level Interviews Analysis

In the process of evaluating the impact of European Union policy on agricultural practices, an analytical approach was taken to examine interviews with relevant stakeholders. This assessment focused on the **implementation of the Sustainable Use Directive (SUD)** and the adoption of **Integrated Pest Management (IPM) strategies**. The analysis uncovered a discrepancy in the application of the SUD across various Member States, indicating a lack of uniformity in enforcement and stringency. Stakeholders reported that this variability has resulted in a fragmented effectiveness of the directive. In discussing policy enforcement, the interviews brought to light the challenge of applying these policies uniformly across the diverse agricultural landscapes of the EU.

While stakeholders demonstrated a **commitment to IPM strategies**, they acknowledged the hurdles faced in widespread implementation. These challenges are exacerbated by current policy frameworks that insufficiently support farmers' transition to sustainable practices. In this context, the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) was identified as a pivotal tool for advancing IPM, with stakeholders calling for clearer obligations and incentives under this policy.

The importance of **data-driven decision-making** was a point of consensus among stakeholders, who highlighted the current deficit in comprehensive and reliable data as a significant obstacle to effective policy-making and farmer support. The influence of public opinion and research findings on policy direction and the adoption of IPM was also underscored, emphasizing the need for ongoing research and the integration of scientific discoveries into policy.

Digital technologies were recognized for their potential to facilitate the application of IPM strategies. However, the actual integration of such technologies with existing agricultural practices remains limited, suggesting a need for more directed policy support.

Furthermore, the integration of various **EU policies** was discussed as a complex yet crucial aspect of promoting sustainable agriculture. Stakeholders indicated the necessity for a more integrated policy framework that harmonizes environmental sustainability objectives with agricultural productivity.

5.1 MS Level Interviews Analysis

1) Germany:

In Germany, policy makers express a shared concern regarding the need to improve the implementation of Integrated Pest Management (IPM) practices among the farming community. They acknowledge the importance of embracing IPM more effectively but express reservations about the imposition of additional regulations by the European Union (EU). Their hesitancy arises from the belief that the existing regulations are sufficiently robust, and the introduction of further rules might introduce complexity and increased costs to the agricultural sector. Their primary focus is on ensuring that any new regulations are pragmatic and do not impose undue burdens.

Germany has taken proactive steps to promote IPM by providing farmers with valuable advice and support, particularly through the integration of modern digital tools designed to protect crops more efficiently. Unlike certain other countries, Germany has not implemented a dedicated tax system aimed at reducing pesticide usage.

Regarding the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) and Germany's own strategies, the interviews do not provide specific details on how these plans intend to reduce pesticide usage through IPM. Additionally, there is no clarity on whether Germany plans to incorporate new ideas from the CAP strategy or align them with the EU's Green Deal goals for 2030.

Germany aims to enhance farmers' knowledge about IPM through the Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation System (AKIS) while ensuring that the advice provided to farmers remains unbiased and not driven by pesticide sales interests. Policy makers recognize that several factors influence IPM acceptance in Germany, including efforts to reduce pesticide usage, promote biodiversity, and maintain effective pest and disease control. Policies are being crafted to suit diverse regions and farming types, acknowledging the importance of tailoring approaches to specific challenges faced by different areas.

Moreover, policy makers prioritize engaging with various stakeholders involved in farming and nature conservation to gather diverse viewpoints. While specific mechanisms for stakeholder involvement are not outlined, the importance of inclusive decision-making is stressed. Policy makers place significant value on research and innovation, with an emphasis on digital tools, predictive techniques, beneficial insects, and other innovative approaches to encourage IPM adoption. Finally, public perception and consumer preferences play a pivotal role in shaping agricultural practices, with a growing demand for pesticide-free products. However, there is a need for increased consumer education about IPM and sustainable farming practices to align consumer expectations with IPM adoption.

2) Italy:

In Italy, there is a consensus among those interviewed about the need for more ambitious policies to enhance the implementation of Integrated Pest Management (IPM). Policy makers believe that clearer rules and specific requirements set by the European Union (EU) would ensure a more consistent application of IPM practices across different countries. Such EU-driven regulations could also facilitate increased funding for training, advisory services, and monitoring to assess the effectiveness of IPM. Italy already employs various tools to support IPM, including comprehensive national guidelines, region-specific regulations known as Integrated Production Specifications (IPS), and quality certification systems like the National Integrated Production Quality System (SQNPI). Policy makers emphasize the importance of tailoring IPM promotion strategies to the specific needs and challenges faced by different regions.

Training for farmers and equipping them with new knowledge, along with exploring alternatives to chemical products, is considered crucial for promoting IPM. Policy makers also highlight the significance of collaboration among farmers, suppliers of farming inputs, retail establishments, and consumers to collectively drive IPM adoption.

Research and innovation are regarded as essential components of effective IPM policies. Policy makers express the existence of ongoing research projects aimed at controlling diseases and

protecting crops, but specific details on these initiatives are not provided. Challenges related to finding safe plant protection products, addressing retailer demands, and understanding the influence of public perception on farming practices are acknowledged.

Policy makers appear willing to support IPM projects through various means, including direct collaboration, financial investment, and the involvement of officials and experts. Additionally, they recognize the importance of maintaining accurate records, potentially through digital tools, for tracking pesticide usage, but emphasize the need for proper farmer training in this regard. Lastly, policy makers see value in collaboration, both within Italy and with other EU countries, to address specific IPM needs and overcome challenges.

3) Belgium:

In Belgium, particularly in the region of Flanders, policy makers are in agreement that the European Union (EU) needs to establish more ambitious and detailed rules for Integrated Pest Management (IPM). They believe that such regulations are essential to ensure consistency across the diverse agricultural systems within Europe. In Flanders, IPM receives support through the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) Strategic Plan, which includes conditions that farmers must meet to receive support and funding for IPM-related investments.

Discussions underscore the importance of finding a delicate balance between reducing pesticide use and ensuring the economic viability of farming operations. While the impact of regional differences on IPM willingness is acknowledged, specific mechanisms to address this are not outlined in the interviews. Policy makers emphasize the use of conditions related to IPM to encourage its adoption, with public awareness and concerns about pesticides playing a significant role in driving IPM practices.

Stakeholder engagement is practiced at multiple levels, with mechanisms ranging from informing and consulting to involving and collaborating with various interest groups. The importance of involving stakeholders in decision-making processes is highlighted, although specific methods or mechanisms for doing so are not detailed in the interviews. Belgium places a strong emphasis on training farmers and providing them with new knowledge, as well as exploring alternatives to chemical products. Policy makers also stress the importance of collaboration among farmers, suppliers, retailers, and consumers to collectively promote IPM adoption. However, specific research initiatives and collaboration with other EU countries in the context of IPM policy are not discussed in detail in the interviews.

4) Poland:

In Poland, policy makers express a unanimous recognition of existing challenges in the effective utilization of Integrated Pest Management (IPM). They highlight issues related to the oversight of IPM practices, a lack of educational efforts, and insufficient knowledge among farmers. Despite legal requirements mandating the recording of IPM activities, it is acknowledged that these obligations are not consistently met. Policy makers universally stress the critical role of educating farmers, citing it as a fundamental factor for successful IPM implementation. They advocate for EU support in educating farmers about IPM principles and the associated regulations, as they identify the lack of farmer education as a primary reason for suboptimal IPM utilization.

While policy makers have reservations about the effectiveness of new EU rules without addressing fundamental implementation challenges, they express uncertainty about the enforcement of new requirements, such as digital records of pesticide use. Public opinion in Poland does influence environmentally friendly farming practices like IPM, but the general public's limited knowledge of sustainable farming practices presents a challenge. Policy makers believe that raising public awareness and promoting sustainably grown products could enhance the popularity of IPM.

Research and innovation are acknowledged as crucial elements of successful IPM policies. Policy makers identify the scarcity of funding and government policies as hindrances to research and innovation in IPM. To improve IPM policies, they advocate for greater support for innovation and technology. Additionally, political and ideological differences within the EU are acknowledged as challenges in amending pesticide-related regulations. Policy makers stress the importance of finding a balanced approach to address these differences and promote IPM policies.

Concerns regarding data collection and verification are raised, particularly with the introduction of digital records for pesticide use. Policy makers express uncertainty about the proper control and verification of such data, given the sheer number of farms.

5) Romania:

Romania acknowledges the need for more effective implementation of Integrated Pest Management (IPM) practices, especially in regions where IPM adoption has been less successful, including small farms. The country is actively working to promote IPM by encouraging farmers to adopt integrated management principles and follow guidelines designed to support IPM methods. Notably, Romania has introduced a pesticide tax as a means to promote IPM practices. The country has also implemented specific measures, such as banning certain chemicals, and mandates the use of IPM assessment forms. The revision of Romania's National Action Plan (NAP) every five years is in line with CAP requirements and allows for the incorporation of new opportunities provided by CAP. Romania also aims to align its activities with the Farm2Fork and Biodiversity strategies.

Starting from January 1, 2026, Romania plans to launch a digital platform that allows farmers to record treatments with plant protection products. This platform will be accompanied by voluntary training for farmers on its usage. Romania is considering expanding the scope of digital records to include information on harmful organisms and active substances used. One of the primary challenges for IPM in Romania is the prevalence of small farms. Policy makers suggest solutions such as using plant varieties resistant to cold, approving low-risk plant protection products, and promoting the use of certified seeds and seedlings. Collaboration with partners is sought to address region-specific IPM challenges.

Supply chain challenges include fostering collaboration among stakeholders, increasing awareness and knowledge about IPM, and ensuring access to information and IPM tools. Policy makers also acknowledge the need for an improved regulatory framework, standards, and the certification of IPM products. While collaboration with supply chain partners is recognized, specific details about how products are differentiated based on IPM principles are not provided.

Romania's approach to stakeholder engagement encompasses informing, consulting, involving, and collaborating with various stakeholders. Policy makers stress the importance of including stakeholders throughout the project, maintaining transparency in project information, and treating

stakeholders as partners. However, there is no detailed mention of collaboration with other EU states to address stakeholder-related issues in IPM policy.

6) Netherlands:

In the Netherlands, it is observed that approximately half of farmers fully embrace the principles of Integrated Pest Management (IPM), with a preference for chemical solutions. However, greenhouse growers tend to incorporate non-chemical methods more frequently than those farming in open fields. The Dutch Ministry of Agriculture, Nature and Food Quality has set ambitious goals in their updated National Action Plan to enhance IPM adoption, including the development of tools to track crop protection methods.

Regarding rule-setting, the Ministry believes that Member States should establish more specific criteria and requirements to accommodate varying growing conditions. Despite this, the Dutch Food Safety Authority advocates for IPM guidelines to become a mandatory part of national laws. Policy makers emphasize the importance of recognizing different regional challenges. For instance, sandy areas have specific concerns about water quality and biodiversity conservation, and the government collaborates with local authorities to address these issues.

In the supply chain, a primary challenge is increasing the sales and consumption of sustainable products. While eco-labels like "PlanetProof" gain popularity, the price disparity between sustainable and regular products remains a significant obstacle.

The policymaking process in the Netherlands involves various stakeholders, with working groups consisting of government officials, business representatives, and interest groups. While the Netherlands actively participates in European working groups and offers training on IPM through the Better Training for Safer Food (BTSF) program, specific collaboration with other EU countries on IPM policy is not detailed. Numerous research projects aim to reduce the use of plant protection products, focusing on precision farming techniques and initiatives like the Green Crop Protection Knowledge Impulse. The Netherlands hosts operational groups as part of the European Innovation Partnership (EIP), which focus on IPM and reducing pesticide usage, overseeing various projects related to sustainable farming and pest management.

7) Denmark:

Denmark acknowledges the challenges associated with effectively implementing Integrated Pest Management (IPM) and emphasizes the significance of both European Union (EU) and national regulations in this context. To encourage the adoption of IPM, Denmark has introduced a pesticide tax and implemented specific measures, including the prohibition of certain chemicals. Denmark also mandates the use of IPM assessment forms as part of its IPM approach.

While Denmark does not offer direct support for IPM through the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) Strategic Plan, the country focuses on promoting organic farming and supporting grassland management. Denmark's small size and consistent agroclimatic conditions mean that region-specific IPM policies are not considered necessary. However, the country acknowledges specialization in crop production within different regions, each facing unique challenges.

Denmark places significant value on stakeholder engagement in policy-making, with a long-standing tradition of involving stakeholders in the development of National Action Plans (NAPs) for pesticide use. While specific mechanisms for involving stakeholders are not outlined in the interviews, the importance of stakeholder inclusion and transparency in project information is stressed. The country's IPM strategy prioritizes farmer education, knowledge-sharing, and the exploration of alternatives to chemical products. Policy makers also highlight the significance of collaboration among various stakeholders, including farmers, suppliers of farming inputs, retail establishments, and consumers, to collectively drive IPM adoption.

Research plays a substantial role in Denmark's IPM approach, with ongoing projects focused on precision application technologies and the establishment of IPM innovation farms. Denmark does not participate in European Innovation Partnership (EIP) operational groups, but it supports IPM research through its national pesticide action plan and other funding mechanisms.

8) Spain

The interviews emphasized the significance of implementing ambitious and well-defined criteria for regulating Integrated Pest Management (IPM) at the EU level. This reflects a commitment to improving IPM practices and addressing challenges in the agricultural sector. The discussion of legislative measures and tax regimes in Spain to reduce pesticide use highlights the country's efforts to promote sustainable agriculture and minimize the environmental impact of pesticides. The role of advisory services and training for farmers in IPM principles indicates a proactive approach to educating and supporting farmers in adopting more sustainable pest management practices.

Identification of specific challenges, such as reducing the use of phytosanitary products in vineyards, underscores the importance of tailoring policies to address the unique needs of different crop clusters and regions within Spain. The discussions on how policies can address these specific challenges and needs indicate a commitment to policy adaptation and improvement to promote IPM practices effectively.

The interviews highlighted the mechanisms used in Spain to involve stakeholders in the policy-making process, demonstrating a commitment to inclusive decision-making. Ensuring adequate representation of stakeholder interests and concerns during policy formulation is essential for crafting policies that are balanced and effective. Collaboration and cooperation with other Member States for stakeholder engagement underlines the importance of sharing best practices and experiences to enhance policy development.

The emphasis on research findings and innovations impacting IPM adoption shows a commitment to staying informed about the latest advancements and leveraging them to improve pest management practices. The existence of European Innovation Partnership (EIP) groups and ongoing research initiatives in Spain highlights efforts to actively engage in research-driven policy development and implementation. The role of awareness, knowledge transfer, and research in supporting IPM-related policies underscores the importance of disseminating information and fostering a culture of innovation in agriculture.

Challenges in the supply chain, such as the need for collaboration, knowledge, awareness, and regulatory standards, are essential considerations in ensuring the effectiveness of IPM practices throughout the agricultural value chain. The potential for supply chain partners to differentiate

products based on IPM principles indicates a recognition of market demand for sustainable and pesticide-free agricultural products.

The influence of public opinion and consumer preferences on agricultural practices, particularly the preference for pesticide-free products, highlights the importance of aligning agricultural policies with evolving consumer expectations. Concerns were raised about the lack of consumer education regarding IPM and the need for greater awareness among consumers regarding sustainable farming practices.

9) Greece

In Greece, several key factors influence the implementation of Integrated Pest Management (IPM) and pose challenges to its acceptance. These factors include concerns about pathogen resistance, a tendency to view IPM as a last resort, and the pressing need for alternative solutions to traditional pesticide-based pest control methods.

The government has made efforts to support IPM through the provision of detailed plant protection guidelines, which are readily available on the Ministry's website. These guidelines cover various plant growth stages and are accessible to both technicians and producers, providing valuable information for implementing IPM practices effectively.

One area that requires improvement is communication between bureaucratic entities and stakeholders. There is a recognized need to bridge the knowledge gap among producers regarding IPM. Enhancing communication channels and providing better education and information to farmers can help promote IPM adoption. Public opinion and consumer preferences play a significant role in shaping agricultural practices in Greece. The increasing demand for "clean" or pesticide-free fruits and vegetables is influencing production chains.

However, it is noted that there is a lack of consumer knowledge about IPM. There is an expectation that better information and awareness campaigns will lead to more sustainable farming practices aligned with consumer expectations. While specific research findings impacting IPM adoption were not mentioned in the responses, there is a general interest in innovations that could be incorporated into IPM policies. This suggests a willingness to adapt and evolve IPM practices based on emerging research and technological advancements.

6. Synthesis of information

6.1 Desktop Research

The SUD provides the framework rules on the use of pesticides. It aims to reduce the risks and impacts of pesticide use on human health and the environment, but it is clear that it does not reflect the strengthened ambitions of the Farm to Fork Strategy to achieve specific pesticide use and risk reduction targets by 2030, as well as to accompany farmers in the transition towards a more sustainable production system. Similarly, it does not do enough to support the long-term objective for a zero-pollution ambition for a non-toxic environment. It is therefore unlikely, as confirmed by stakeholder views, that the ambition of the European Green Deal can be achieved with the current provisions of the SUD (Ramboll et. al, 2022).

The SUD also aims to promote the use of integrated pest management (IPM) and alternative approaches or techniques, such as non-chemical alternatives to pesticides. Reducing the use of pesticides has never been an explicit policy objective of the SUD. It was assumed that the implementation of IPM and an increased use of alternative methods to control pests would lead to a reduction in the use of pesticides and, as a result, to a reduction of the risks for and impact on human health and the environment.

The European Commission in its [2020 report](#), on the progress of the implementation of the SUD, concluded that the assessment of the implementation of IPM by the Member States continues to be the most widespread weakness in the application of the directive. The implementation of IPM practices varies across EU countries due to legal, behavioural, environmental, and resource-related factors. Notable differences exist in the application of IPM principles, with some farmers not following the recommended intervention hierarchy. Reasons for this variation include differences in policy frameworks, legal interpretation, agricultural practices, climatic conditions, capacity constraints, and vested interests. Capacity limitations, including lack of knowledge and resources, hinder implementation, emphasizing the importance of support measures. Tradition, environmental conditions, and farmers' willingness also contribute to differences in IPM adoption (EC, 2023).

The Commission considered IPM as one of the cornerstones of the SUD, and that its full implementation is necessary in order to reduce dependency on pesticide use. However, it does not define how the eight general principles of the IPM are to be applied in practice, leaving their definition to Member States. Following the principle of subsidiarity, these criteria need to be determined at national, or even sub-national level, given the diversity of agriculture between, and within Member States, in terms of climate, crops grown and production techniques. However, Member States have not converted the IPM general principles into prescriptive and assessable criteria to be applied by users. Therefore, Competent Authorities do not have prescriptive and assessable criteria in order to determine compliance with IPM, and therefore there is limited evidence that IPM is systematically applied. Member States have failed to exploit the significant potential for greater adoption of IPM, including the more widespread adoption of non-chemical pest control techniques (EC, 2020).

One problem seems to be that there is not enough understanding of, and adherence to, IPM guidelines. So, while IPM implementation is an obligation under the SUD – many farmers still do not have access to materials, guidelines and IPM protocols for their specific situation. CropLife Europe believes that this gap needs to be filled and that knowledge sharing needs to be accelerated. One way to facilitate the promotion and dissemination of IPM strategies is by creating a centralized database accessible to farmers, agronomists and advisory services at European, national and regional levels. The Pilot Project, “Farmer’s Toolbox for Integrated Pest Management”, has developed a [public database](#) of IPM practices and crop- and sector-specific guidelines gathered from the EU

Member States, with the ambition to disseminate the database across the EU as a source of inspiration for farmers and farmers' advisors (EC, 2023). However, the lack of a specific definition for these guidelines led to considerable variation in document nature, creating challenges in their identification. Some countries focus on production sectors rather than specific crops. While most guidelines aim to provide farmer guidance, some, like those in Belgium, also serve for control and verification by authorities.

On 22 June 2022, the Commission submitted a proposal for a revision of the SUD. The SUR proposal proposes legally binding SUR pesticide reduction targets at EU level to reduce by 50% the use and the risk of chemical pesticides and the use of the more hazardous pesticides by 2030, and proposes measures to improve IPM, where chemical pesticides can only be used once all non-chemical options are exhausted. The SUR proposal obliges Member States to adopt legally binding SUR national pesticide reduction targets corresponding to the SUR EU pesticide reduction targets. A significant feature of the proposal for revision is the upgrade of the directive to a regulation, i.e., it would be directly applicable in its entirety in all Member States, and therefore seeks uniform implementation of the EU rules at national level. The proposal for revision is based on a large number of information sources, among them an ex-ante impact assessment (ex-ante IA), a complementary impact assessment and an ex-post evaluation⁶ – supported by externally prepared studies at the Commission's request, the Commission's reports on the implementation of the SUD published in 2017 and 2020, a foresight study on future vision scenarios on the sustainable use of pesticides,⁸ various stakeholder consultation activities, etc.

As stated by the inception impact assessment of the revision of the SUD published on 29 May 2020, the main problem, which triggered the revision, is the limited effectiveness of the implementation of the directive, i.e., its failure to achieve the main objective of reducing the risks that the use of pesticides poses for human health and the environment. The revision thus aims to improve certain aspects of the design and practical implementation of the directive, in order to: significantly reduce the use of pesticides that are PPPs and the risks they pose; the dependency on pesticides; and enhance the IPM approach. A complementary IA conducted in early 2023, confirms the conclusion of the evaluation and impact assessment that there is a need to revise the SUD to address important policy issues such as poor and variable implementation across Member States, the lack of national targets and the need to protect sensitive areas. It further reaffirms the objectives of the SUR proposal and the SUR pesticide reduction targets, noting that since the SUR proposal was adopted the EU and all EU Member States have adopted the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework at the Fifteenth meeting of Parties to the United Nations Convention on Biological Diversity (COP15) and subscribed to a globally binding target of 'reducing the overall risk from pesticides and highly hazardous chemicals by at least half including through integrated pest management (IPM), based on science, taking into account food security and livelihoods' by 2030. This global target is fully in line with the SUR pesticide reduction targets set out under the SUR proposal.

The SUR proposal includes steps to increase the implementation of IPM. The IPM general principles set out in the SUR proposal need to be translated into clear crop-specific rules to be implemented by farmers and to enable checks by national authorities. This does not mean that more demanding voluntary recommendations, beyond binding rules, may not be developed by national authorities to complement the implementation of the general principles, these voluntary practices being eligible to classical CAP financing. Depending on the Member State, certain IPM practices can be part of the requirements of conditionality and therefore not supported by additional CAP payments (on the basis of their eligibility criteria). This support would only be allowed for improvements that go beyond the baseline requirements of SMR and GAECs. Other such IPM practices designed by Member States as voluntary may therefore be funded by eco-schemes and management commitments. However, to support the transition towards an ambitious reduction in the use of pesticides, the Commission has

proposed, in the SUR proposal, a derogation to allow additional funding, through the CAP Funds, for implementing obligations resulting from the SUR Regulation – even if normally required as SMRs or GAECs (thus in the baseline) – during a period of 5 years after its entry into force. Member States may thus, if the SUR Regulation were adopted as proposed, choose to provide additional funding for these practices related to pesticide reduction. There is, nevertheless, no ‘new’ money provided for by the SUR proposal in the CAP budget and Member States will have to use the available budget. The SUR proposal also includes the promotion of independent advice that is intended to facilitate the farmer to make relevant decisions on a case-by-case basis.

During bilateral discussion held between DG SANTE and Member States’ authorities regarding the progress made in achieving reductions in the Farm to Fork pesticide reductions targets, many Member States highlighted the positive correlation between the implementation of IPM and progress toward achieving the Farm to Fork pesticide reduction targets. Success factors for IPM implementation include linking IPM with financial support, targeted training for farmers, and the availability of a broad set of crop-specific IPM guidelines. However, other Member States expressed concerns about the potential to further reduce pesticide use based on IPM implementation as the current level of implementation was suggested to be close to its maximum.

The Commission does not always have the granular and Member State specific data, and particularly on pesticide use, that Member States have, which limits the ability to provide Member State and crop-specific analysis. The application of IPM is not systematically recorded nor required to be recorded in most Member States. Member States are required to ensure that professional users keep records of their pesticide use, but there is no legal requirement for the government to collect these records from users. The level of official controls on pesticide use in Member States is limited. Even though the use of pesticides is legally required to be recorded at farm level, these data are not systematically collected or analysed leading to the lack of available comparable data on the use of specific plant protection products (e.g., how, when, where, why they are used, and the exact products used). In the future, the SAIO Regulation will provide valuable statistics on pesticide use to enable more precise monitoring of progress towards further pesticide reduction targets. Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2023/564 as regards the content and format of the records of plant protection products kept by professional users will require pesticide use records to be in electronic form in all Member States from 1 January 2026. Compulsory electronic pesticide use records are already in place in Member States such as Denmark and planned to become compulsory in Spain. Additionally, the FSDN Regulation aims to collect farm level data on sustainability that will contribute to the improvement of advisory services to farmers and benchmarking of farm performance. Like the FADN, the FSDN will provide a common and harmonised survey to collect farm level economic, environmental and social data and make data comparable at EU level. Data will be collected about both the use of plant protection products and farming practices, such as integrated pest management.

A key barrier to the promotion of IPM practice is the lack of availability of alternatives to chemical plant protection products and conventional practices. Promising alternative solutions (biopesticides, techniques and technologies) may exist but are often still at development level. Moreover, the effectiveness of such alternatives is generally lower as compared to conventional products. This results in an additional effort by the farmers that need to combine several techniques, thus requiring advanced know-how. Furthermore, the regulatory framework for placing alternative products on the market remains too cumbersome and the time for registration of such products continues to increase (EC, 2023). However, it should be noted that several measures to increase the knowledge and spreading of holistic IPM principles and relevant tools are already in progress, strongly supported by research and innovation. The Commission has already established a legal framework for accelerated approvals of low-risk and biological control pesticides (such as data requirements for approval of

microorganisms) and is taking steps to extend this to a broader range of types of biocontrol (IA SUR compl). The Commission has also suggested how the colegislators might consider certain possible changes during negotiations that might further facilitate the market in low-risk and biological control pesticides. With the framework provided by the Commission, with action being taken by industry and with Member State authorities setting the appropriate priorities and providing the necessary resources, it appears that sufficient tools will be available within the timeframe of the SUR pesticide reduction targets to achieve the required reduction in chemical pesticide use and risk without unacceptable implications on food security or food affordability

Only four NAPs (Belgium, Denmark, France and Germany) set an overall quantified pesticide risk reduction target, and only Denmark and Germany link this to a measure of environmental risk. The overall objective of the NAP should show a reasonable level of ambition, but the majority of revised NAPs lack ambition. This is illustrated in the case of Spain, a Member State with almost one million farms⁵⁵, setting a target of at least 2 pilot farms to promote IPM (EC, 2020)). Even in its recently revised NAP, this target is set to 8 pilot farms.

In line with the European Commission and European Court of Auditors' assessment, Helepciuc and Todor analysis (2022) confirms that despite progress, even the second generation of NAPs does not fully address the limitations identified in the Commission report. Promoting IPM is present in some of the objectives but there is no systematic approach to monitoring progress by using a clear set of harmonized risk indicators that would allow to monitor and compare the progress toward the policy objectives of SUD. While substantial progress is still needed, the current analysis shows that imposing an approach that only sets general goals without a clear quantification and clear requirements for a common approach to the measures, timetables, and indicators has yet to achieve the goals of SUD. Limited monitoring of the impact of pesticides on the environment and human health makes it difficult to assess the impact of NAPs (Remáč et al., 2018).

The implementation of IPM practices varies across EU Member States due to legal, behavioural, environmental, and resource-related factors. Notable differences exist in the application of IPM principles, with some farmers not following the recommended intervention hierarchy. Reasons for this variation include differences in policy frameworks, legal interpretation, agricultural practices, climatic conditions, capacity constraints, and vested interests. Capacity limitations, including lack of knowledge and resources, hinder implementation, emphasizing the importance of support measures. Tradition, environmental conditions, and farmers' willingness also contribute to differences in IPM adoption.

National competent authorities (NCAs) play a crucial role through information dissemination, financial support, and regulatory control. Financial support is central for farmers transitioning to sustainable practices. Compliance control varies among Member States and it would be more effective if proper targets related to IPM were established.

Market preferences and public opinion have a limited impact on reducing pesticide use, but consumer interest in sustainable and healthy food benefits organic and IPM production. However, challenges include consumer confusion about IPM labels, unclear recognition, and valuation of IPM products. Willingness to pay for reduced pesticide exposure varies across demographic segments, with factors like brand, price, and product type influencing purchasing decisions. The pilot project concluded that stakeholders express concerns that farmers are not sufficiently rewarded for their IPM efforts, and

⁵⁵ Available at:

https://appsso.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/nui/show.do?dataset=ef_m_farmleg&lang=en

the price premium may not reach them, depending on market structure in different EU Member States. Various public and private schemes target reducing pesticide use, with organic farming and zero pesticides showing promise. However, in-between solutions like IPM labels with reduced pesticide use face challenges in marketing. Private certification schemes promoting pesticide reduction struggle due to low demand and consumer awareness, except in the fruit and vegetable sector. The potential of private schemes is hindered by limited consumer demand and awareness beyond organic certification, with only a few schemes in Europe, primarily in specialty crops. In specific cases, such as the French case study, vegetable growers in producer organizations initiated a "Zero pesticides" label to reduce dependency on pesticides. Operational programs could facilitate the establishment of quality labels at the national level based on agro-environmental interventions. Consumer awareness and willingness to pay (WTP) for organic food have increased, but understanding and appreciation of IPM as a production system remain weaker. Communicating IPM is challenging due to the complexity of principles covered. Unique schemes like mountainous farming have a limited association with reduced pesticide use, mainly benefiting farms in mountainous areas that are less dependent on pesticides and are often specific to individual stakeholders.

The 2009 SUD foresaw the possibility of the IPM becoming part of the conditionality rules of the CAP. However, the CAP legislation for the 2014-22 period did not include the SUD in the statutory management requirements for farmers. The European Commission's report of October 2017 concluded that Member States had not developed clear criteria to assess the implementation of IPM principles in controls at the farm level and have not taken appropriate measures to deal with non-compliance in this regard. The second report in 2020 reached the same conclusion. The European Court of Auditors (ECA, 2020[42]) concluded that Member States undertake only very limited control of farmers to verify that IPM principles are implemented, and as that IPM implementation is not a condition for receiving CAP payments, there is little development of non-chemical alternatives and little incentive for farmers to take them up. Several Member States request that farmers fill out a form with information on how they have applied for IPM. However, the forms are currently not checked by inspectors to determine compliance with the principles of IPM. The inception impact assessment of the revision of the SUD confirmed that the link between the SUD and the CAP is strong in theory, but weak in practice.

The CAP 2023-2027 framework includes the scope for Member States to set a strong mandatory baseline of requirements that make up the basis for IPM in the Good Agricultural and Environmental Conditions (GAEC) for crop rotation, buffer strips along water courses, cover crops, and at least 4% of area under landscape features and fallow or nitrogen-fixing crops in which pesticides are not used. However, it does not include reference to the SUD Article 14 requiring farmers to apply IPM. There is, therefore, no mandatory requirement in the CAP that specifies that farmers have to make plans to reduce pesticide use and prove that they are applying IPM in order to receive direct payments. Eco-schemes, agri-environmental commitments and investments can then be used to provide incentives for farmers to apply IPM or to carry out practices that support IPM.

According to the ex-ante evaluations of the CSPs, their relevance is high in terms of economic needs and moderate for rural development and environmental needs. Contributions to European Green Deal objectives are included throughout the 28 CSPs, but are largely unquantified and unspecified. The eco-schemes, together with the agri-environment and climate measures including organic farming and strengthened conditionality, are likely to contribute to the objectives. The extent of contribution, however, will depend on the uptake and implementation of the eco-schemes and the management commitments. Pesticide use is also a highly relevant EGD objective with respect to the agricultural sector. CSPs recognise the importance of reducing the use and risks of chemical

pesticides and more harmful pesticides, although national levels are rarely set, implementation strategies of planned instruments are often unclear, and significant differences in the extent and approach to reducing pesticide use and risks are noted (Münch et al. (2023).

Belgium, Spain, Italy, and the Netherlands are identified with elevated levels of pesticide sales per hectare, exceeding 5 kg/ha. On the other hand, Germany, Greece, France, and Poland exhibit intermediate levels of pesticide sales per hectare, ranging between 2 and 5 kg/ha. Denmark and Romania, in contrast, demonstrate lower pesticide sales per hectare, falling below 2 kg/ha. Despite the different levels of pesticide sales, all of the countries except France present reduced risks and impacts associated with pesticides (EC, 2023).

Belgium, Germany, Greece and Italy refer to several interventions in their CSPs aimed at facilitating the attainment of EU pesticide targets, such as integrated pest management, non-chemical control, precision and organic farming, presence of landscape features, and knowledge and cooperation interventions. BE-Wallonia, Germany and Romania have established national targets in their CSPs, with the objective of reducing the use and risk of chemical pesticides by 50%. Notably, these targets are set without a specific deadline for achievement. Belgium, Germany and Greece also refer to measures under national pesticide legislation, outside the CSPs, that support pesticide reduction. The Netherlands supports pesticide use reduction mainly without CAP funding. Denmark, France, Poland and Spain do not provide national targets or any information on the intervention logic supporting the achievement of the EGD pesticide targets through CAP funding or with instruments outside the CAP.

All CSPs identify the general need for reducing the use of chemical pesticides and implementing integrated pest management and they plan to address pesticide reduction. The SUPPORT countries show different levels of ambition towards the reduction of pesticide use and specifically the promotion of IPM practices in their CSPs. Overall, Denmark, Spain, Greece, France, Italy, Poland and Romania have set a high priority to the need to reduce use of chemical pesticides and promote integrated pest management while Belgium, Germany and Netherlands indicated a lower need to reduce use of chemical pesticides and promote IPM (EC, 2023).

The CSPs support a wide range of farm practices that can contribute to address pesticide reduction, including limitations to the use of pesticides on agricultural land, alternatives to chemical pesticides such as biological and mechanical protection methods, the use of buffer strips, crop rotation, landscape features as well as precision farming, training and advice and other risk management and collaborative tools. The farm practices on plant protection are supported through conditionality, eco-schemes, agri-environmental and climate commitments, sectoral interventions, investments, precision farming, training, advice and cooperation. Denmark, Spain, Greece, France, Italy, Poland and Romania promote IPM as a high priority, while Belgium, Germany and the Netherlands as a medium priority. Although many of the practices supported by CSPs contribute to Integrated Pest Management (IPM) (e.g. crop rotation, mechanical pest control, optimising synthetic pesticide application), few CSPs specifically support the implementation of IPM as a comprehensive approach to the holding (e.g. where a combination of individual measures are designed to have synergistic effects on pest control taking into account local conditions). IPM is supported through eco-schemes in Poland, Greece and Italy and through AECM in Spain. Spain and Italy also support the development of pesticide management plans through AECM. IPM as a whole is supported in Poland, Greece, Italy and Spain. The rest CSPs support IPM-related practices. COM report NOV23

The correlation between the R.24 CAP indicator and the objectives outlined in the European Green Deal (EGD) is somewhat fragile. Overall, 26.6% of EU agricultural land is planned to be subject to support specifically requiring reduction or more sustainable use of pesticides (beyond requirements of conditionality) in the CSPs in total. Belgium-Wallonia, Germany, Greece, France, and Italy exhibit

a noteworthy commitment to achieving sustainable and reduced pesticide usage in their CSPs. Notably, France has set the indicator at an ambitious 61%, which is the highest among the EU Member States. In contrast, Spain, the Netherlands, Romania and Poland have established less ambitious targets, with percentages of 5%, 7%, 8% and 9,4%, respectively. BE-Flanders and Denmark have set intermediate targets. It is important to realize that the result indicators in the PMEF do not consistently capture intervention results or outcomes. Evaluations at EU and Member State level should feature significant ambition in the assessment of results and link them to the related interventions. Member States opted to target a number of significant needs specified in the CAP Strategic Plans with other policies and tools outside of the CAP. It is recommended that evaluation efforts are conducted, covering not only the CAP Strategic Plans, but also the national and EU policy instruments contributing to these goals.

EU-funded research and innovation projects develop, demonstrate and disseminate IPM solutions, which are made available through thematic and advisory networks, supporting farmers in the transition towards the sustainable use of pesticide. In addition, the Copernicus programme, the Earth observation component of the EU's Space programme, is now helping to simplify and modernise CAP monitoring through offering detailed and timely information on crops and farmland.

Beyond the CAP, Member States may also use national funds to promote the reduction in use and risk of pesticides by means of various approaches adapted to the national context (taxation, certificates of pesticides sparing, financial instruments, etc.).

6.2 Interviews Analysis

Across the EU, there is a recognized variability in the adoption and effectiveness of IPM strategies. Member states report a spectrum of implementation levels, with some countries noting that a substantial portion of growers do not fully apply IPM principles, often defaulting to chemical pesticides as a primary control method. This variability is partly attributed to the different agricultural landscapes and climatic conditions present in the EU, which necessitate region-specific approaches to pest management. In Denmark and the Netherlands, for example, the uniformity of agroclimatic conditions does not warrant region-specific IPM policies. In contrast, countries with more varied conditions require tailored strategies to address unique regional challenges, such as water quality issues in sandy soil regions of the Netherlands or pathogen resistance observed in Greece.

The synthesis of interviews underscores that economic incentives and clear policy frameworks are pivotal in encouraging the uptake of IPM. Denmark's use of pesticide taxes exemplifies an economic tool designed to motivate farmers towards IPM practices. On the other hand, Germany's reliance on technological advancements and advisory services points to a multifaceted approach, coupling economic measures with knowledge dissemination and innovation. The Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) emerges as a central instrument in supporting IPM, yet its application and strategic emphasis on IPM differ among member states. While some countries, like Belgium, integrate IPM promotion through CAP conditionality and investments, others like Denmark do not directly support IPM in their CAP Strategic Plan, focusing more on organic production and grassland support.

Engagement with stakeholders is a common thread in the formulation of IPM policies. Member states recognize the value of incorporating diverse perspectives, from farmers and businesses to conservationists and the public. However, the interviews reveal a discrepancy in the quality and extent of this engagement. While Denmark and Belgium have established traditions of inclusive dialogues, other member states are still striving to improve stakeholder involvement in the policy-

making process. Public opinion plays a significant role in shaping agricultural practices and policy directions. Consumer demand for products with minimal pesticide residues is driving changes in the production chain, as noted by responses from Greece and the Netherlands. However, there is also a recognized need for better public education on IPM to inform consumer choices and support sustainable practices.

Innovation and research are identified as crucial drivers for advancing IPM-related policies. The development and adoption of digital tools, forecasting models, and alternative control methods are highlighted by countries such as Germany, where these technologies are integral to the national IPM strategy. Despite the potential, the actual integration of these innovations into agricultural practices varies, with some countries like Poland and Romania citing funding issues and the need for better support for innovation.

6. Conclusion - Policy Gaps and Needs

Sales and use of plant protection products across Europe vary greatly depending on the type and level of agriculture and is dominated by the largest agricultural producers. In 2021, 355.175 tonnes of PPPs were sold in the EU. This was a moderate increase in sales of 2.7% compared with 2020 (346.000 tonnes) and represented a further rebound back towards the medium-term annual average between 2011 and 2021. Among EU countries, the volume of pesticides sold in 2021 were highest in Spain (21% of the EU total), France (20%), Germany and Italy (both 14%), the EU's main agricultural producers. In Poland (8%), Netherlands (2.6%), Romania (2,4%), Belgium (1.6%), Greece (1.3%) and Denmark (0,8%), the volume of pesticides sold in 2021 was 57.907 tonnes. Compared with 2011, Denmark, Italy, Romania, Belgium and Netherlands recorded a decrease in the sales of pesticides in 2021, while Spain, Germany and France recorded a slight increase. About Poland and Greece there is not available data (Eurostat). For the OECD, reductions in pesticide use in France, Germany, Italy, Poland, and Spain, which account for half of the pesticide sales by weight in the European Union, would have a large effect overall, while changes in smaller users would be less likely to be reflected in overall values (OECD, 2023).

HRI 1, measuring the use and risk of pesticides, shows a decrease of 38% since the baseline period in 2011-2013 and a 6% decline compared to 2020. HRI 2, which is based on the number of emergency authorisations, shows an increase of 41% since the baseline period in 2011-2013 and a 3% decrease compared to 2020 (EUROSTAT, 2023). The Commission considers that full IPM implementation and an increased use of alternative methods to control pests is necessary in order to reduce dependency on pesticide use. Nevertheless, reducing the use of pesticides is not an explicit objective per se of the SUD. While many of the SUD provisions have been implemented in most Member States, and likely contributed to a reduced risk of pesticide use as suggested by the decrease of HRI1, this finding is not consistent across other indicators (i.e., observed decrease in biodiversity in rural ecosystems, MRL exceedance trend and the increase in HRI2, which indicates the limitations of the ability to definitively state whether there has been a reduction of risk (Ramboll et al., 2021).

The Commission's 2017 and 2020 reports on SUD implementation to the European Parliament and the Council, EPRS (2018), ECA evaluations and the recent impact assessments in the framework of the revision of the SUD, have concluded that **the SUD has only been moderately effective as a policy instrument**. Although IPM is seen as a key element in the sustainable use of pesticides, and many local examples of good practice can be seen (EC, 2023), the assessment of the actual implementation of IPM through Member State controls and corresponding enforcement has been weak (ECA, 2020). This results in **limited evidence on the effective implementation of IPM across the EU**. The Commission 2020 report included a compliance-monitoring index to quantify progress in the implementation by and between Member States, which revealed a particularly poor implementation of the SUD provisions with regard to IPM enforcement (34% implementation by 2019) and NAPs (53%). Many Member States **do not set quantitative targets or indicators in their NAPs** to promote the sustainable use of pesticides or better protect human health and the environment. The SUD is also criticised by industry stakeholders and pesticide users as limiting technological innovation, (e.g. drones and other precision farming techniques), which might have the potential to reduce overall dependency on pesticides and associated risks to human health and the environment.

The latest SUD impact assessment report (EC, 2022) has confirmed the weaknesses in the implementation and enforcement of IPM and limited effectiveness of Member State NAPs. Member State competent authorities face challenges in controlling and enforcing IPM due to its principle-based nature, the **absence of clear definitions and criteria**, making it difficult to assess the actual level of implementation. Despite the environmental and economic advantages offered by IPM, it is not consistently adopted by most farmers. Possible reasons include **unclear rules on IPM application, insufficient incentives, training, and advice** in certain Member States (as reported in 2017 and 2020), or a **lack of alternatives in specific crop-pest combinations**. Additional factors include the **absence of clear tools for monitoring** IPM implementation and enforcement, a perception among pesticide users and industry stakeholders that market pesticides are safe and

effective, and a reluctance to take specific actions to reduce their use. Some stakeholders may believe there are **no equally effective alternatives** to chemical pesticides or may wish **to avoid disadvantaging pesticide users** in one Member State compared to others with potentially less restrictive pesticide policies in non-EU countries.

The Commission and other stakeholders have concluded that considerable deficiencies remain in the implementation of the SUD's requirements to apply IPM. This is especially evident in the challenge of translating the general principles of IPM into **assessable criteria** for supporting, monitoring and enforcing IPM practices at the farm level. Another obstacle lies in the insufficient availability of **practical guidelines** that address crop- and sector-specific requirements, as well as of integrated approaches to cropping systems that combine various techniques for pest control. Establishing specific rules can effectively translate IPM requirements into measurable criteria applicable to a particular crop in a specific region.

Additionally, there is a **shortage of practical alternatives** in the form of biological, physical and non-chemical methods for pest control. Biological control agents offer a sustainable alternative to the use of chemical products in managing harmful organisms. As noted in Council Decision (EU) 2021/1102⁵⁶, biological control agents have a growing importance in sustainable agriculture and forestry and have an instrumental role to play in the success of IPM and organic farming.

The Commission does not always have the granular and Member State specific data, and particularly on pesticide use, that Member States have, which limits the ability to provide Member State and crop-specific analysis. Improving the **availability of data** on pesticide use is particularly important for monitoring IPM implementation. The current lack of reliable indicators or data on pesticide use or how IPM is implemented in practice do not allow to correctly assess progress made. To better achieve the objectives of the SUD, it is considered that crop protection practices would need to change, meaning that pesticides users change how and when they apply pesticides to control pests. The competent authorities lack the information necessary to verify whether a professional user has carried out a decision-making process, in accordance with integrated pest management, before determining a specific preventative measure or intervention and the reasons for that. Regulation (EU) 2022/2379 of the European Parliament and of the Council will in the future provide valuable statistics on pesticide use to enable more precise monitoring of progress towards further pesticide reduction targets and effective IPM implementation. Additionally, the FSDN Regulation aims to collect farm level data on sustainability that will contribute to the improvement of advisory services to farmers and benchmarking of farm performance. Like the FADN, the FSDN will provide a common and harmonised survey to collect farm level economic, environmental and social data and make data comparable at EU level. Data will be collected about both the use of plant protection products and farming practices, such as integrated pest management.

Better training and specific record-keeping requirements on IPM could be helpful in ensuring that the overall potential of the SUD and IPM in particular is better achieved. Member States need to establish and maintain systems of both initial and follow-up training for distributors, advisors and professional users of plant protection products and certification systems to record such training, in order to ensure that those operators are fully aware of the potential risks to human health and the environment and of the appropriate measures to reduce those risks as much as possible. The training for advisors should be more extensive than that of distributors and professional users since they

⁵⁶ COUNCIL DECISION (EU) 2021/1102

Council Decision [\(EU\) 2021/1102](#) of 28 June 2021 requesting the Commission to submit a study on the Union's situation and options regarding the introduction, evaluation, production, marketing and use of invertebrate biological control agents within the territory of the Union and a proposal, if appropriate in view of the outcomes of the study, OJ L 238, 6.7.2021, p. 81–83

need to be able to support the proper implementation of integrated pest management and crop-specific rules. In order to ensure a planned approach to harmful organism control techniques across a number of growing seasons with a view to minimising the use of chemical plant protection products as much as possible and to ensure a proper implementation of integrated pest management, professional users should be required to regularly consult trained, independent advisors on pest management, so that plant protection products are only used as a last resort. It should be noted that pesticide user respondents to the public consultation, for the revision of the SUD, stated that, following participation in a training course, their knowledge improved considerably. Additional training could therefore also be a viable tool to improve the implementation of IPM by pesticide users.

It should also be noted that several measures to increase the knowledge and spreading of holistic IPM principles and relevant tools are already in progress, strongly supported by **research and innovation**. Developments in application modes to reduce pesticide use relate both to the use of different platforms (e.g. unmanned aerial vehicles, spraying robots) as well as technological components included in tractor-mounted sprayers. Such developments are crop and location specific. Arguably, precision farming approaches and the use of digital and data technologies in general, can and should go hand in hand with other farming/ production approaches, such as IPM, organic farming or agro-ecology. In many cases the use of precision farming technologies result in reducing inputs which generate a saving to the farmer. A key hurdle in the adoption of IPM and novel technologies is the uncertainty farmers face regarding their effectiveness and proper use, and sometimes the high investment costs (e.g. of precision agriculture tools). In order to overcome this, advice and demonstration of practices, including farmer to farmer learning, as well as outreach directly to farmers, is crucial to support their confidence in transitioning to low-pesticide management systems.

Concerning efficiency, the direct costs of SUD implementation (training, inspections, IPM) mainly fall on the professional users of pesticides, in particular farmers, who on the other hand have little direct economic benefit from implementing SUD provisions. This is likely one element hindering or challenging the full implementation of the Directive at farm level.

Concerning coherence, national policies regarding the sustainable use of plant protection products and the promotion of IPM are not standardized, and their alignment with the goals of important EU flagship initiatives, such as the European Green Deal, the Farm to Fork Strategy, and the Biodiversity Strategy, is not evident. The conceived link between the SUD and the CAP is strong, but in practice it is weak. Potential measures under the CSPs could incentivise farmers to a greater extent to contribute to the Green Deal targets to reduce the use and risk of chemical pesticides by at least 50% in 2030 at EU level. Enhanced conditionality and voluntary interventions will likely contribute to the Green Deal ambition to reduce the use and risk of chemical pesticides by 2030, although the extent of the contribution is too early to determine. Although the majority of the CSPs do not report national target values regarding the use and risk of pesticides, the majority of the CSPs provides an overview of how it will contribute to EU Green Deal targets. Regarding pesticides, conditionality now includes provisions of the Directive on sustainable use of pesticides (SUD) as a new SMR as well as GAEC standards relevant for the sustainable use of pesticides and Integrated Pest Management that are strengthened compared to the previous period. This includes requirements on crop rotation and biodiversity areas, contributing to a reduced need to use chemical pesticides. Voluntary schemes offer support to a large range of farm practices on pesticide management, from measures to further restrict the use of synthetic pesticides, to supporting the uptake of alternative forms of plant protection. The CSPs generally support the range of measures expected to be implemented under Integrated Pest Management (IPM). However, the concept as a whole is frequently not explicitly supported by the CSPs. Where this is not the case, this may hinder an effective implementation of IPM as its effectiveness will depend on the coherent uptake of several practices to reduce pressures from pests and diseases. About half of the CSPs contain explanations of national efforts to achieve the targets on pesticides outside the CAP, and several of the CSPs stress that the elements outside the CSP represent the main instruments in supporting pesticide management, in particular.

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ANNEX I

Interview guidelines for Member State Policy Makers

INTRODUCTION

This interview questionnaire has been designed in the context of the project SUPPORT, which is funded under the Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme for a period of four years (January 2023-December 2026). SUPPORT is a joint initiative of 20 organisations from 10 different countries, including academia and higher education, SMEs, farmer cooperative organisations, and public bodies.

With the primary goal of facilitating the adoption of Integrated Pest Management (IPM) tools, strategies, and technologies, SUPPORT aims to develop relevant and actionable knowledge to be used in co-creation design with actors of public policies and private sector strategies. One specific objective of the project is to propose recommendations for improving public policies that enhance the adoption of IPM tools and technologies. In alignment with this objective, a policy analysis will be conducted. This analysis aims to identify policy gaps and propose recommendations aiming at improving policies specific to regions, cropping systems and agri-food supply chain. The following questionnaire will be utilised to conduct interviews with policy makers at European Union and Member State levels, enabling the exploration, comparison and contrast of needs and challenges within diverse policy environments.

Four specific study themes have been identified, around which the questionnaire has been designed:

1. **Theme 1:** Assessment of the existing IPM related policy frameworks at Member State level and of the effectiveness of their implementation.
2. **Theme 2:** Identification of specific needs and challenges related to IPM principles in different regions and in relation to different cropping systems and agri-food supply chain within the Member States.
3. **Theme 3:** Examination of stakeholder engagement in the IPM-related policy making process.
4. **Theme 4:** Assessment of the role of research and innovation in shaping IPM-related policies.

Information provided will be treated according to GDPR rules. Information will be anonymised.

For more information on the project, please refer to our website: www.he-support.eu.

Should you need any clarification, please get in touch with us at: kalliopi.kounani@aia.gr

IDENTIFICATION QUESTIONS

Date of the interview	
Country	
Name of the authority/ organisation	
Name of the interviewee	
Position of the interviewee	
Email	

A. Are you willing to be contacted for follow-up questions after the interview?

Yes No

THEME 1 - Policy Framework Assessment

Under Theme 1, we want to identify and assess the current Integrated Pest Management (IPM)-related policies, strategies and initiatives at your country. For this, we want to understand the objectives, the components and the key elements of the existing IPM-related policy framework, what activities you undertake in your country to ensure the uptake of IPM by farmers, how you monitor the implementation and how you evaluate the effectiveness of the IPM related policy framework. In addition, we would like to explore if your CAP Strategic Plan (CSP) includes tools to promote IPM and how do you plan to implement the new legal framework to collect data on pesticide use.

1. Previous evaluations and reports have concluded that IPM is poorly implemented. Our assumption is that more ambitious policy options could contribute to the improvement of the implementation of IPM in the Member States:

1.1. Do you agree with that statement?

Yes No

1.2. If yes, do you think that more sharply defined criteria and more specific requirements in relation to IPM need to be regulated at EU level and why?

1.3. If no, please provide your reasoning.

2. How do you encourage the application of IPM in your country? Do you have in place specific measures, such as legal requirements, guidelines, financial or technical support measures, trainings etc?

3. Do you have a specific tax regime in place to reduce the use of pesticides?

Yes No

3.1. If yes, how is the generated tax used?

CAP Strategic Plan (CSP)

4. How instruments of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) targeting the reduction of pesticide use (GAEC, SMRs⁵⁷, AECM⁵⁸, eco-schemes⁵⁹, others) are integrated in your CAP Strategic Plan?

5. Which funding opportunities supporting the uptake of IPM by farmers have you included in your CSP?

6. To which extent have you planned to update your National Action Plan (NAP) based on new opportunities provided in your CSP?

7. The Farm2Fork⁶⁰ and Biodiversity⁶¹ strategies set targets to reduce pesticides risk and use. In your MS, to which extent are such targets integrated into your CSP?

8. Do you think that the result indicator R24⁶² on pesticides that you have set up in your CSP allows your country to contribute to the 2030 targets of the European Green Deal?

⁵⁷ GAEC (Good Agricultural and environmental conditions) and SMR (Statutory and mandatory requirements) are elements of the conditionality of CAP payment linked to the fulfilment of certain environmental criteria.

⁵⁸ Agri-environment-climate commitments (AECM), which are considered to be beneficial to achieving a sustainable and reduced use of pesticides, in particular pesticides that present a risk for human health or environment, including implementing Integrated Pest Management techniques

⁵⁹ Eco-schemes that include actions for a sustainable and reduced use of pesticides, in particular pesticides that present a risk for human health or environment, including implementing Integrated Pest Management techniques

⁶⁰ Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions - A Farm to Fork Strategy for a fair, healthy, and environmentally friendly food system, 20.5.2020, COM/2020/381 final. Available [here](#).

⁶¹ Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions, EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030, Bringing nature back into our lives, 20.5.2020, COM/2020/380 final. Available [here](#).

⁶² Sustainable and reduced use of pesticides: Share of utilised agricultural area (UAA) under supported specific commitments which lead to a sustainable use of pesticides in order to reduce risks and impacts of pesticides such as pesticides leakage

9. Member States have the obligation to provide advisory services to farmers through the Farm Advisory Services (FAS). Do you foresee additional measures under the AKIS scheme to train farmers on IPM principles?

Yes No

- 9.1. If yes, please provide the description of the measures or link.

- 9.2. Are there measures in place to keep advisory services independent from sales of pesticides?

Yes No

- 9.3. If yes, please provide the description of the measures or link.

Data on pesticides and IPM

10. Are you familiar with the provision of Regulation (EC) 2023/564⁶³, which requires professional users of plant protection products to maintain digital records of the products they use, beginning on January 1, 2026?

Yes No

- 10.1. How do you plan to adapt your national system to this legal requirement, inform the farmers, train them and put in place the needed procedure?

- 10.2. Member States have the possibility to require the users to include other information in combination with the records required under Article 67(1) of Regulation (EC) No 1107/2009 (digital record keeping). Do you plan to require other type of data?

Yes No

- 10.3. If yes, what kind of data?

- 10.4. The application of IPM is a legal requirement under the current SUD but is not systematically recorded nor required to be recorded in most Member States. Do you consider requiring data on IPM, such as records of preventative measures and interventions for crop protection by professional users, and of advice on use of plant protection products?

Yes No

- 10.5. Do you plan, as a competent authority, to establish electronic registers to keep records of the use of plant protection products, records of preventative measures and interventions for crop protection by professional users, and of advice on use of plant protection products?

⁶³ COMMISSION IMPLEMENTING REGULATION (EU) 2023/564 of 10 March 2023 as regards the content and format of the records of plant protection products kept by professional users pursuant to Regulation (EC) No 1107/2009 of the European Parliament and of the Council

Yes No

10.6. If yes, how do you plan to utilize the collected data and information to improve the implementation and outcomes of IPM-related policies within your country?

11. Which synergies or trade-offs do you observe in pursuing EU objectives, such as pesticide use and risk reduction and food security, simultaneously?

THEME 2 - Specific needs and challenges

Under Theme 2, we aim to understand what are the specific needs and challenges that you face in your country related to IPM implementation specific to different regions and different cropping systems and agri-food supply chain. We are further interested in understanding better what factors influence the uptake of IPM practices in different cropping systems and how they affect the policy design.

Region-specific needs and challenges

12. Are there any specific factors affecting the acceptance and use of IPM related to regional specificities in your country? Please explain, if any.

12.1. If any, how do you ensure that IPM-related policies are tailored to meet the region-specific requirements of IPM implementation in your country?

13. Are there any region-specific IPM initiatives, collaborations or partnerships in place to address region-specific challenges?

Yes No

13.1. If yes, please provide information and links.

13.2. Do you consider endorsing any of these initiatives by including them into national IPM-related policies and how?

Crop/cropping system-specific needs and challenges

14. Have you identified specific needs and challenges related to IPM implementation about the crops of your National Crop Clusters⁶⁴, selected in the framework of SUPPORT?

Yes No

14.1. If yes, please explain about each crop.

14.2. How do the IPM-related policies in your country address the above challenges and needs?

14.3. Could you please share information about any initiatives, collaborations, or partnerships in your country that are being implemented to address the aforementioned challenges, specific to each crop?

14.4. Do you consider endorsing any of these initiatives by including them into national IPM-related policies and how?

Supply-chain related needs and challenges

15. What are the main supply-chain requirements and challenges related to IPM in your country? (*You can choose multiple answers*)

- Collaboration and coordination among different stakeholders (farmers, distributors, retailers, consumers)
- Knowledge and awareness
- Access to information and IPM tools
- Regulatory framework and standards
- Certification of IPM products
- Training and capacity building
- Data sharing and traceability
- Other, please specify

16. Do you consider that the supply chain partners (such as retailers) would differentiate their product supply based on IPM principles production?

⁶⁴ In the framework of the project 25 National Crop Clusters (NCCs) will be used for data collection. NCCs are a selection of cases covering a wide range of farm typologies, sectors and systems representative of the diversity of farming in the EU and associated countries. The NCCs include wheat, maize, onion, potato, strawberry, apple, wine grape and olive. These crops were selected for their empirical diversity and suitability in studying the IPM techniques, barriers and drivers in different food sectors, with vastly different production methods and unique sustainability challenges. In identifying the NCCs, a balance has been sought between annual vs. perennial crops; specialty products vs. commodities; broad geographical spread in different climatic zones. **Please ask about the crops included in your NCC**

17. Are there any collaborations or partnerships within your country to address supply chain-related needs and challenges in IPM?

17.1. Do you consider endorsing any of these initiatives by including them into national IPM-related policies and how?

18. To which extent does public opinion and/or consumers' willingness to buy sustainable products have an impact on agricultural practices, such as IPM, in your country?

THEME 3 - Stakeholder engagement

Theme 3 focuses on the examination of stakeholder engagement in the IPM-related policy making process in your country.

19. What approaches or mechanisms are used to engage stakeholders in the IPM-related policy-making process in your country?

20. How do you ensure that the interests and concerns of various stakeholder groups are adequately represented during the IPM-related policy-making process?

21. Are there any lessons learned or best practices in stakeholder engagement that you can share?

22. How do you collaborate and cooperate with other member states to address stakeholder needs and challenges in relation to IPM-related policies?

THEME 4 - Role of research and innovation

Theme 4 focuses on the assessment of the role of research and innovation in shaping IPM-related policies. We further explore how awareness and knowledge transfer help to enhance the uptake of IPM practices and support the design of IPM-related policies.

23. Are there any specific research findings or innovations that have had a positive impact on the adoption of IPM in your country, specifically concerning the crops within your NCC? If so, please specify those findings or innovations that you have already incorporated or intend to incorporate into your IPM-related policies.

24. Are there European Innovation Partnership (EIP) Operational Groups financed through your Rural Development Programme (at national or regional level) working on issues related to the IPM or pesticide use reduction?

Yes No

- 24.1. If yes, please provide information on any projects that can contribute to the development of IPM-related policies.

25. Are there any other ongoing research initiatives or projects in your country that are specifically dedicated to IPM and can contribute to the development of IPM-related policies? Please, specify.

Interview guidelines for EU Policy Makers

INTRODUCTION

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With the primary goal of facilitating the adoption of Integrated Pest Management (IPM) tools, strategies, and technologies; SUPPORT aims to develop relevant and actionable knowledge to be used in co-creation design with actors of public policies and private sector strategies. One specific objective of the project is to propose recommendations for improving public policies that enhance the adoption of IPM tools and technologies. In alignment with this objective, a policy analysis will be conducted. This analysis aims to identify policy gaps and propose recommendations aiming at improving policies specific to regions, cropping systems and agri-food supply chain. The following questions will be utilised to conduct interviews with policy makers at EU level, enabling the exploration, comparison and contrast of needs and challenges within diverse policy environments.

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IDENTIFICATION QUESTIONS

Date of the interview	
Country	
Name of the authority/ organisation	
Name of the interviewee	
Position of the interviewee	
E-mail	

A. Are you willing to be contacted for follow-up questions after the interview?

Yes No

1. Previous evaluations and reports have concluded that IPM is poorly implemented. Our assumption is that more ambitious policy options could contribute to the improvement of the implementation of IPM in the Member States:

1.1. Do you agree with that statement?

Yes No

1.2. If yes, which gaps, in the implementation of the Sustainable Use Directive, do you think hinder achieving its objectives to promote the use of IPM and of alternative approaches or techniques, such as non-chemical alternatives to pesticides?

1.3. If no, please provide your reasoning.

2. The application of IPM is a legal requirement under the current SUD but is not systematically recorded nor required to be recorded in most Member States. Do you think that more sharply defined criteria and more specific requirements in relation to the implementation of IPM need to be regulated at EU level?

Yes No

2.1. If yes/no, please provide your reasoning.

3. Weaknesses remain in the implementation of the SUD in some Member States and specifically deficiencies in controls relating to IPM. Do you think that the Commission should consider a range of actions?

Yes No

3.1. If no, why?

3.2. If yes, what kind of actions?

3.3. If the Commission were to consider including infringement procedures in these actions, do you believe they would effectively ensure the implementation of IPM in the Member States. Please provide your reasoning.

3.4. Do you consider that sanctions would have a positive impact on IPM uptake at farm level? Please provide your reasoning.

4. Which synergies or trade-offs do you observe in pursuing EU objectives, such as pesticide use and risk reduction and food security simultaneously?

5. The Commission has put forward a proposal for a Regulation on the Sustainable Use of plant protection products (SUR). If the legislative procedure will not be finalised during the current parliamentary term, do you believe that this will adversely affect the promotion of IPM in the Member States and why?

6. The Commission has put forward a proposal for a regulation on nature restoration⁶⁵ aiming to contribute to the continuous, long-term and sustained recovery of biodiverse and resilient nature across the EU's land. How would the adoption of this proposal affect the promotion of IPM in the Member States?

7. The Commission has put forward a proposal on plants obtained by certain new genomic techniques, Do you believe that NGT plants will effectively hinder the dependency on pesticide use, and if yes, how this would affect the promotion of IPM in the Member States?

⁶⁵ Proposal for a REGULATION OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL on nature restoration - COM/2022/304 final

8. In the Farm to Fork Strategy, the Commission announced a proposal for a sustainability-labelling framework to empower consumers to make informed and sustainable food choices. Do you believe that such a framework would promote IPM uptake in Member States and how?

9. The Farm to Fork strategy puts forward the ambition for 2030 to reduce nutrient losses by at least 50%, while ensuring that there is no deterioration in soil fertility. This will reduce the use of fertilisers by at least 20% by 2030. To which extent will this future restriction of the use of fertilisers contribute or hinder the dependency on pesticide use, and how this could affect the promotion of IPM in the Member States?

10. The SAIO⁶⁶ Regulation establishes an integrated framework for aggregated European statistics on agricultural inputs and products, including statistics on the sales and use of plant protection products on an annual basis. Do you believe that the existence of a robust database on the crops and pests on which these pesticides are used, could promote the implementation of IPM in the Member States and why?

11. Do you see current or upcoming EU policies, other than the above, that are related to IPM and how?

12. Do you believe that digital technologies and precision crop management can provide forward-looking solutions to the reduction of the use of pesticides and promote IPM uptake in Member States and why?

13. Do you think that utilising Behavioural Science, thus green nudges as an agri-environmental policy tool, would affect farmers' decision-making process in favour of adopting IPM States and why?

14. Do you consider that the instruments of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) targeting the reduction of pesticide use (GAEC, SMRs⁶⁷, AECM, eco-schemes, others) if integrated in Member States CAP Strategic Plans (CSP) would have a significant impact on IPM uptake and why?

⁶⁶ Regulation (EU) 2022/2379 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 November 2022 on statistics on agricultural input and output, amending Commission Regulation (EC) No 617/2008 and repealing Regulations (EC) No 1165/2008, (EC) No 543/2009 and (EC) No 1185/2009 of the European Parliament and of the Council and Council Directive 96/16/EC

⁶⁷ GAEC (Good Agricultural and environmental conditions) and SMR (Statutory and mandatory requirements) are elements of the conditionality of CAP payment linked to the fulfilment of certain environmental criteria.

14.1. Which of these instruments do you think would best facilitate the uptake of IPM and why?

15. Member States have the obligation to provide advisory services to farmers through the Farm Advisory Services (FAS) in their CSPs. Do you believe that such measures foreseen under the AKIS scheme to train farmers on IPM principles in the Member States' CSPs would promote IPM uptake at farm level and how?

16. Do you think that the targets, set up for the result indicator R24⁶⁸ on pesticides in Member States' CSPs, allow the EU to achieve the 2030 targets of the European Green Deal and how?

17. Even though the use of pesticides is legally required to be recorded at farm level, these data are not systematically collected or analysed leading to the lack of available comparable data on the use of specific plant protection products. Regulation (EC) No 2023/564⁶⁹ requires professional users of plant protection products to maintain records of the products they use, beginning on January 1, 2026, in digital format. How can this new obligation promote the IPM uptake in Member States?

18. How is ensured that the interests and concerns of various stakeholder groups are adequately represented in the EU when developing IPM-related policies?

19. The issue of pesticide use is highly polarized in the EU, creating significant barriers to regulatory changes. How can these barriers be effectively eliminated?

⁶⁸ Sustainable and reduced use of pesticides: Share of utilised agricultural area (UAA) under supported specific commitments which lead to a sustainable use of pesticides in order to reduce risks and impacts of pesticides such as pesticides leakage

⁶⁹ COMMISSION IMPLEMENTING REGULATION (EU) 2023/564 of 10 March 2023 as regards the content and format of the records of plant protection products kept by professional users pursuant to Regulation (EC) No 1107/2009 of the European Parliament and of the Council

20. To which extent does public opinion have an impact on sustainable agricultural practices such as IPM?

21. How does research and innovation results influence the formulation and implementation of IPM related policies in the EU?

22. Are there any other policy topics related to IPM that we have not covered and you wish to share with us?